

Prediction bands for the individual treatment effect

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1 Introduction

Over the last decades, extensive statistical theory has been developed in the identification, estimation, and uncertainty quantification of the average treatment effect (ATE) under the potential outcome framework (e.g. Rubin (1974), Pearl (1995)). The ATE however is only a coarse summary statistic of the distribution of treatment effects and can be misleading when considering an intervention. This is particularly relevant in medicine: Imagine that a drug cures 80% of the treated patients, while it substantially aggravates the symptoms for the remaining 20%. It is certainly a question of perspective whether the drug should be approved, even given a positive average treatment effect. Similar issues arise in the discussion of vaccination strategies in the light of the current pandemic: While the benefits of a large scale immunization for society as a whole are considered to be greater than its costs, for some types of patients a doctor might come to the conclusion that the negative side effects dominate.

Treatment effect heterogeneity is of concern in many fields, and has led researchers to target the conditional average treatment effect (CATE) instead. I will introduce a formal definition thereof in Chapter 4, but for now we can think of it as the expectation of an individual level treatment effect (ITE) conditional on the value of the individual's covariates. The CATE provides by definition a richer summary than the ATE, averaging over a more targeted group of samples, but it still neglects the inherent variability in the response¹, which might be crucial for decision-making. This creates a trade-off: On the one hand, we need sufficiently many covariates to explain away a significant fraction of the variability in the response, while on the other hand, increasing the number of observables makes it more difficult to produce a good estimate of CATE for every value in covariate space, given a finite number of observations. Furthermore, in sensible areas such as medicine, point estimates of the CATE are insufficient to inform decisions due to the huge damage potentially incurred by wrong actions. Despite the importance of uncertainty quantification, theoretical guarantees on pointwise confidence intervals for the CATE are still rare, and if existent, usually require strong non-verifiable assumptions and asymptotic regimes that researchers do not encounter in practice. Even for those point estimators enjoying theoretical appeal in terms of consistency and convergence rates, empirical work has shown that they exhibit unsatisfactory coverage in finite samples, even in very simple and smooth models.²

In this thesis, I take a different perspective and leverage ideas from the literature on conformal inference to construct valid *prediction intervals* for the individual treatment effect itself, in the context of the potential outcome framework (Splawa-Neyman, Dabrowska,

¹In particular it abstracts from the part of the response's variability which cannot be explained by the observable covariate vector.

²As documented by Dorie et al. (2019) and Hahn, Dorie, and Murray (2019), a key empirical finding from direct comparisons of various methods in competitions is that, while many of the methods perform well with regard to metrics such as the root-mean-squared error or the bias, nominal coverage of confidence intervals is not achieved by any estimator.

and Speed (1990), Rubin (1974)). In particular, I compare and investigate non-trivial estimated intervals with reliable coverage on individual effects for subjects not in the study, and for which both potential outcomes are missing.

The major benefit of this approach is a guaranteed *finite sample coverage* of the generated prediction intervals, absent strong assumptions. As we will see, this finite sample guarantee is unfortunately only valid on average (and not conditionally on observables). However, while results on *pointwise asymptotic coverage* of confidence intervals on the CATE are limited to a small selection of estimators, the portrayed prediction intervals are agnostic to their base learner and satisfy *asymptotic conditional coverage* on the ITE for any consistent machine learning method. In practise, this increases the chances substantially to find a better approximation of our target function, since we can adapt our tooling to the data generating process flexibly, and consequently get closer to conditional coverage than would be possible with confidence intervals. Furthermore, prediction intervals take the inherent variability in the response into account by construction, making it an attractive approach for high-risk settings.

After a short literature overview in Chapter 2, Chapter 3 begins by introducing the concepts of predictive inference and conformal inference in a *regression setting*. Based on that we will contrast some of the most promising conformal procedures that have been suggested in the literature, both in terms of theoretical support as well as their empirical performance. Against that background, Chapter 4 argues how conformal inference from the regression setting translates to the potential outcome framework and individual treatment effects, given the fundamental problem of causal inference. Along this line, we will discuss some recent suggestions of candidate intervals for the ITE and compare the necessary assumptions behind each method. Finally, I will present some new power considerations on those prediction intervals, both in terms of a theoretical oracle band, as well as in a simulation study.

2 Related Literature

Conformal inference The framework of *conformal inference* has been pioneered by V. Vovk and colleagues in the 1990s and provides a tool for achieving finite sample coverage of prediction intervals in a distribution free setting. The book by Vovk, Alex Gammerman, and Shafer (2005) is often considered the definitive reference; see also Shafer and Vovk (2008) for a practical guide, Vovk, Nouretdinov, and Alex Gammerman (2009) for an application to linear regression, Papadopoulos, Vovk, and Alexander Gammerman (2011) for an application to *k-nn* regression, Burnaev and Vovk (2014) for efficiency considerations, and Papadopoulos, Proedrou, et al. (2002) for a computationally feasible split sample variant.

Recent developments of this method in the areas of nonparametric and high-dimensional regression can be found in J. Lei and Wasserman (2014) and J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018), with notable extensions to an heteroskedastic setting being introduced by Romano, Patterson, and Candes (2019), Chernozhukov, Wüthrich, and Zhu (2019) and Kivaranovic, Johnson, and Leeb (2020). Tibshirani and Foygel (2019) develop an important generalization of the conformal method to settings where the fundamental exchangeability assumption breaks down, and in which shifts of the covariate distribution between training and prediction sets need to be accounted for.³

Finally, some authors have applied the conformal concept to prediction sets for the individual treatment effect within the potential outcome framework, with notable contributions being Kivaranovic, Ristl, et al. (2020) and L. Lei and Candès (2020). The former authors develop their prediction bands in a randomized controlled trial setting, while the latter ones focus on observational studies and utilize results from Tibshirani and Foygel (2019).

Heterogeneous treatment effects A second strand of literature related to our objective is concerned with uncertainty quantification on heterogeneous treatment effects. Wager and Athey (2018) establish asymptotically valid coverage of their confidence intervals on the CATE (under regularity assumptions) by using a normal approximation. Künzel et al. (2019) employ resampling techniques to estimate the variance of their CATE estimator, on which they construct confidence intervals. Bayesian Additive Regression Trees (BART), originally developed as a general purpose bayesian machine learning algorithm by Chipman, George, and McCulloch (2010), was later applied to causal inference by J. L. Hill (2011) and Hahn, Murray, and Carvalho (2020) and found to outperform competing methods in terms of coverage (see Hahn, Dorie, and Murray (2019), Dorie et al. (2019)). Interestingly, the generated bayesian credible intervals for the CATE can be replaced with prediction intervals, such that the method can be adapted to cover the ITE, an idea which is explored in L. Lei and Candès (2020).

3 Conformal inference in regression

3.1 Predictive Inference

I will start developing concepts in a regression setting.⁴ To this end, consider the sequence of random vectors $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^n$, with $(X_i, Y_i) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}$, and suppose we are interested in predicting a range for the new response Y_{n+1} , at a test point X_{n+1} . I assume that all the

³As we will see in Chapter 9, an interesting application of this extends to the potential outcome framework.

⁴The term regression setting is often used in the conformal literature and comprises setups where we have draws of a dependent variable, Y , and a covariate vector, X . It does not refer to methods of linear regression.

samples $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^{n+1}$ are drawn exchangeably from an arbitrary joint distribution \mathcal{P}_{XY} .⁵ Conceptually, we are therefore targeting a *prediction band*⁶ that contains the unknown response Y_{n+1} with a pre-specified probability, given *finite data*. Since we wish to make use of the information contained in the observed covariates during the construction of our prediction intervals, we could in principle be interested in two types of *coverage guarantees*: For $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, a random set $\mathcal{C}(X_{n+1}) \subset \mathbb{R}$ is said to have *marginal coverage*, if

$$(1) \quad \mathbb{P}(Y_{n+1} \in \mathcal{C}(X_{n+1})) \geq 1 - \alpha$$

where the probability is taken over the joint distribution of $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^{n+1}$. In other words, \mathcal{C} contains Y_{n+1} at level $1 - \alpha$ on average across all possible values of X_{n+1} , but it is not guaranteed that the interval will cover Y_{n+1} conditional on a particular observed value $X_{n+1} = x$. On the other hand, we say $\mathcal{C}(X_{n+1}) \subset \mathbb{R}$ to satisfy the stronger *conditional coverage*, if

$$(2) \quad \mathbb{P}(Y_{n+1} \in \mathcal{C}(X_{n+1}) \mid X_{n+1} = x) \geq 1 - \alpha$$

Naturally, the latter concept embeds a much stronger guarantee⁷ and might be considered closer in spirit to *pointwise confidence bands*, which are frequently considered in the conventional statistical literature. However, note that in contrast to inference based on *confidence sets*, we do not construct sets for non-random *structural parameters*, but instead generate a random set \mathcal{C} which includes a *random vector* with a pre-specified probability.

Ideally, our prediction intervals should satisfy the conditional coverage from (2), and be as narrow as possible for each point in covariate space. Consequently, a naturally desirable oracle prediction interval would be

$$(3) \quad \mathcal{C}^*(X_{n+1}) = [q_{\frac{\alpha}{2}}(X_{n+1}), q_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}(X_{n+1})],$$

where $q_\alpha(x)$ denotes the α -quantile of the conditional distribution of $Y_{n+1} \mid X_{n+1} = x$. This oracle is desirable, since it is by construction the narrowest symmetric prediction interval that has valid conditional coverage.⁸

Unfortunately, it turns out that (non-trivial) conditional coverage of prediction intervals as in (2) cannot be attained by any estimator in finite samples in a distribution-free setting, as pointed out in J. Lei and Wasserman (2014) and Foygel Barber et al. (2021). For

⁵Exchangeability is slightly weaker than requiring an *i.i.d.* sequence. A definition can be found in Appendix G.

⁶In the following I will use the terms *prediction band* and *prediction interval* interchangeably. This follows common practise in the conformal literature, see for example J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018); although in principle, one could make a distinction, for our main focus on *marginal coverage* it should not matter.

⁷For a further discussion of the difference between the two concepts in the context of conformal prediction, I refer to J. Lei and Wasserman (2014) and Foygel Barber et al. (2021).

⁸Symmetric in the sense that Y_{n+1} is equally likely to be smaller or larger than predicted.

example, the intuitive strategy to replace $q_{\frac{\alpha}{2}}(X_{n+1})$ and $q_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}(X_{n+1})$ in (3) by conditional quantile estimates might sometimes work well in practice, but does not satisfy the coverage statement (2) or even the weaker statement (1) in finite samples, since poor estimates of complex quantile functions can introduce substantial undercoverage through overfitting or bias.

Therefore, we will in the following consider a strategy that is able to generate prediction intervals with marginal coverage in finite samples, and later describe under which additional restrictions on \mathcal{P}_{XY} these intervals can achieve (optimal) conditional coverage asymptotically.

3.2 Full conformal inference

Given a basic understanding of predictive inference and of our objective, we can continue and examine *conformal inference*, which is one of the major concepts in the literature to generate prediction bands with real marginal coverage in finite samples. Before going into the construction itself, let me state a key component underlying the conformal framework, which is a result about rank statistics.⁹

Lemma 1 (Uniform ranks). *Let U_1, U_2, \dots, U_{n+1} be exchangeable random variables with continuous joint distribution. Then for a given $i \in \{1, \dots, n+1\}$ the rank statistic*

$$R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i) \equiv \sum_{j=1}^{n+1} \mathbb{1}(U_j \leq U_i)$$

is uniformly distributed on $\{1, \dots, n+1\}$. Furthermore, for $t \in \mathbb{R}$, we have

$$\mathbb{P}(R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i) \leq t) = \min \left\{ \frac{\lfloor t \rfloor}{n+1}, 1 \right\}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n+1,$$

where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ denotes the floor function.

For completeness, a proof is given in Appendix B, but the result should make intuitive sense. Note that instead of demanding a continuous joint distribution, we could break ties at random and get the same result; in practise this requirement seems to be rather weak and should hold in most cases.¹⁰

Every conformal inference procedure starts by defining a *score function* s , whose arguments consist of a point $(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}$, and a multiset Z .¹¹ Intuitively, for a given (x, y) , a low value of $s((x, y), Z)$ indicates that (x, y) *conforms* to the set Z , whereas a high value

⁹Note that the result can equivalently be stated in terms of quantiles of the empirical distribution.

¹⁰The breaking of ties, or equivalently, the continuity assumption, yields a form of anti-conservativeness in the following theorems. This assumption is not essential for the marginal coverage to hold, however it seems rather weak and is therefore made throughout the rest of this work.

¹¹To be explicit, by passing Z as a multiset, the score function s cannot accept the points in Z in any particular order, but it must take them in as unordered.

indicates that it is atypical. However, since in our regression setting the focus is usually on intervals for the dependent variable Y , all score functions in subsequent chapters will measure nonconformity only in the dependent variable.

The next step generates so called *nonconformity scores* from the chosen score function s . At this point however, conformal methods differ in the way they use the observed sample to induce nonconformity scores. Let us start with the original procedure by Vovk, Alex Gammerman, and Shafer (2005), which is often referred to as the *full conformal method*.

Definition 1. Let $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^n$ be exchangeable random vectors and let $s : (\mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}) \times \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a score function, where \mathcal{Z} is the domain of the multiset Z . Given a point $(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}$, define the **full nonconformity scores** as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{(x,y)} &\equiv s((X_i, Y_i), \{X_j, Y_j\}_{-i} \cup \{(x, y)\}), \quad i = 1, \dots, n \\ V_{n+1}^{(x,y)} &\equiv s((x, y), \{X_i, Y_i\}_{i=1}^n) \end{aligned}$$

Example 1. Consider the score function $s((x, y), Z) \equiv |y - \hat{\mu}(x)|$, where $\hat{\mu} : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a regression function that was trained by running an algorithm \mathcal{A} on $\{(x, y)\} \cup Z$. Applying this score function to the sample $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^n$, we induce the full nonconformity scores

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{(x,y)} &= |Y_i - \hat{\mu}_y(X_i)|, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \\ V_{n+1}^{(x,y)} &= |y - \hat{\mu}_y(x)| \end{aligned}$$

Definition 1 determines the full nonconformity scores for a fixed point $(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}$. In theory, we can repeat the procedure for each $y \in \mathbb{R}$ and replace x by the random vector X_{n+1} .¹² This generates a sequence of sets of scores, on the basis of which we can define the level $(1 - \alpha)$ -full conformal prediction band as follows

$$\begin{aligned} (4) \quad \mathcal{C}_{full}(X_{n+1}) &\equiv \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R} : \left(\sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \mathbb{1} \left\{ V_i^{(X_{n+1}, y)} \leq V_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, y)} \right\} \right) \leq \lceil (1 - \alpha)(n + 1) \rceil \right\} \\ &= \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R} : R_{1:(n+1)} \left(V_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, y)} \right) \leq \lceil (1 - \alpha)(n + 1) \rceil \right\} \end{aligned}$$

In words, this prediction band excludes the values $y \in \mathbb{R}$ for which the induced nonconformity score evaluated at that point, $V_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, y)}$, are too extreme compared to the scores from the rest of the sample. For a more explicit characterisation of this quite general setup, I have added Algorithm 1 in Appendix E which goes through all necessary steps for the score function from Example 1. The next theorem shows that this construct, in particular the symmetry of our nonconformity scores, guarantees exact coverage in finite samples.

Theorem 1. Let $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^{n+1}$ be exchangeable random vectors. Given some score function s , suppose that the induced full nonconformity scores from Definition 1, when being eval-

¹²In practise, we will use a fine grid of values on the real line as an approximation.

uated at $y = Y_{n+1}$, obey a continuous joint distribution. Then for any $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ it follows that the full conformal prediction band in (4), satisfies

$$1 - \alpha \leq \mathbb{P}(Y_{n+1} \in \mathcal{C}_{full}(X_{n+1})) \leq 1 - \alpha + \frac{1}{n+1}.$$

A (rank-based) proof of the theorem can be found in Appendix B. The line of argument is straightforward, taking into consideration the exchangeability of the nonconformity scores, and then applying Lemma 1.

Remark 1. *1 Assuming a continuous joint distribution of scores is only relevant for the upper bound in the result (i.e. anti-conservativeness), which was first pointed out by J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018). The lower bound (i.e. finite sample marginal coverage) is a standard property of all conformal inference procedures and is due to Vovk, Alex Gammerman, and Shafer (2005).*

2 While in principle, \mathcal{C}_{full} does not have to be an interval, taking the supremum and infimum of this prediction set yields an interval. In practise however, in almost all cases the estimated discrete approximation of \mathcal{C}_{full} corresponds to an interval form.

3.3 Split-conformal inference

While the above construction entails nice finite sample properties, the process of building full conformal prediction bands can become computationally expensive, though this of course depends on the choice of our score function s . Consider the use of absolute residuals as in Example 1. As an inspection of Algorithm 1 illustrates, we need to recompute the nonconformity scores for each new covariate value where inference is desired, and for all $y \in \mathbb{R}$. This in turn involves a refitting of our regression estimate $\hat{\mu}$ for each such combination. This can become a major bottleneck especially for high-dimensional settings where sophisticated algorithms to estimate $\hat{\mu}$ might be employed.

Therefore, a fast alternative, known as the *split conformal method*, has been suggested in the literature (Papadopoulos, Proedrou, et al. (2002), J. Lei, Rinaldo, and Wasserman (2015)), which circumvents possible computational limitations by separating the fitting step and subsequent ranking steps via sample splitting.¹³ In other words, the functional shape of the score function s is not learned on the part of the data that is used for computing nonconformity scores, but instead on some preliminary data set. This fixation of the functional shape of s in a preliminary step renders any inference conditional on this part of the data, and inevitably raises an issue of selective inference, which is not further explored in the following.¹⁴

¹³A computational complexity analysis of conformal methods can be found in the work of Papadopoulos (2008).

¹⁴One direction that J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018) explore is to consider multiple splits of the data in order to reduce the additional randomness caused by sample splitting. They show in their Theorem 2.4

Let us formalize this idea in mathematical terms. We begin by randomly splitting our sample into two sets $\mathcal{I}_1, \mathcal{I}_2$. Based on this partition and some score function s , define the induced *split nonconformity scores* as follows

Definition 2. Let $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^n$ be exchangeable random vectors, let $s : (\mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}) \times \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a score function, and $\mathcal{I}_1, \mathcal{I}_2$ be a random partition of $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^n$. Given a point $(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}$, define the *split nonconformity scores*

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{V}_i &\equiv s((X_i, Y_i); \mathcal{I}_1), \quad i \in \mathcal{I}_2 \\ \tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(x,y)} &\equiv s((x, y); \mathcal{I}_1).\end{aligned}$$

where we consider the set \mathcal{I}_1 in the argument as a fixed parameter to determine the functional class, and the first argument as the point of evaluation.

Example 2. Consider the score function $s((x, y), Z) \equiv |y - \hat{\mu}_Z(x)|$, where $\hat{\mu}_Z : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a regression function that was trained by running an algorithm \mathcal{A} on Z . Applying this score function to the partition $\mathcal{I}_1, \mathcal{I}_2$ of $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^n$, we induce the split nonconformity scores

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{V}_i &= |Y_i - \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_i)|, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}_2 \\ \tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(x,y)} &= |y - \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(x)|\end{aligned}$$

It is crucial to understand that the training of any estimator (for example $\hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}$) is limited to observations in \mathcal{I}_1 , while its evaluation to generate the split conformity scores is on $\mathcal{I}_2 \cup (x, y)$. This independence of the functional shape of s from the new point (x, y) essentially gives us the ability to avoid the retraining of our estimator for every $y \in \mathbb{R}$ and instead yields a single condition for all candidates of our prediction set. Note that in comparison to the full nonconformity scores, we discard information during the training of our score function, a fact which might provide some intuition for the empirical finding that the split conformal method generates intervals that are often slightly wider than their full conformal counterparts.¹⁵ However, although we can lose a slight amount of efficiency (in terms of interval lengths), the split conformal method generates savings in computational terms and, in metaphor, lets us invest a lot of resources into the finding and fitting of an optimal base learner algorithm.¹⁶

that under rather general conditions the resulting intersection of prediction bands from multiple splits gets wider as the number of splits increases, suggesting to only use a single split in practise.

¹⁵For a detailed comparison between the full conformal and split conformal method in a regression setting, I refer the interested reader to J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018).

¹⁶Some authors such as Linusson et al. (2014) go so far as to argue that the full conformal approach can thus be less efficient than the split version, and that the loss of accuracy introduced by splitting the sample is usually negligible relative to the gain in resources for fitting a suitable estimator. Here accuracy describes how well an estimator (a prediction rule) inside a score function approximates the true population parameter, and efficiency is equivalent to the width of the resulting prediction intervals after conformalization.

The split nonconformity scores in Definition 2 eventually lead us to a specification for the level $(1 - \alpha)$ -*split conformal prediction band*,

$$(5) \quad \mathcal{C}_{split}(X_{n+1}) \equiv \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R} : \tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, y)} \leq V_{(k)} \right\}$$

where $k = \lceil (1 - \alpha)(|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1) \rceil$, and $V_{(k)}$ is the k -th order statistic of the set $\{\tilde{V}_i : i \in \mathcal{I}_2\}$. We will later see that for many special cases of score functions, this prediction set can be written as an interval. At that note, I have again added Algorithm 2 in Appendix E to summarize the steps in building \mathcal{C}_{split} , for the split nonconformity scores from Example 2. Eventually, the next result shows that the general finite sample marginal coverage carries over to the split conformal setting.

Theorem 2. *Let $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^{n+1}$ be exchangeable random vectors. Given some score function s , suppose that the induced split nonconformity scores from Definition 2, when being evaluated at $y = Y_{n+1}$, obey a continuous joint distribution. Then for any $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ it follows that the split conformal prediction band in (5), satisfies*

$$1 - \alpha \leq \mathbb{P}(Y_{n+1} \in \mathcal{C}_{split}(X_{n+1})) \leq 1 - \alpha + \frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1}.$$

A proof can be found in Appendix B. Note further that the statements from Remark 1 carry over to this setup as well. The anti-conservative upper bound, which depends on the cardinality of the set on which we generate the nonconformity scores, is slightly larger than in the full conformal setting, since we have made use of sample splitting.

3.4 Classes of score functions

So far we have established interval procedures that achieve finite sample marginal coverage in a distribution free setting, but at the same time abstracted from optimality considerations, such as bounds on the resulting interval lengths. Also, recall that one of our main objectives is to find conditions on the score function s , and the sample distribution \mathcal{P}_{XY} , such that our conformal prediction band asymptotically converges to the optimal oracle in (3).

To this end, I will in the following describe some popular types of score functions, together with corresponding model restrictions, under which the induced conformal prediction bands asymptotically achieve the efficiency of the oracle, including its conditional coverage guarantee. Since I later wish to compare the finite sample performance of these different candidates in simulations, I focus on the split conformal variants in each class for the sake of computational feasibility.

3.4.1 Mean-based scores

To begin with, let us focus on a situation where our data comes from a model with homoscedastic, symmetric noise; that is we assume the following,

- A1** (*i.i.d.* data) We observe *i.i.d.* data $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^n$ from a common distribution \mathcal{P}_{XY} on $\mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}$, with conditional mean function $\mu(x) = \mathbb{E}(Y | X = x)$
- A2** (Independent and symmetric noise) For $(X, Y) \sim \mathcal{P}_{XY}$, the noise variable $\epsilon = Y - \mu(X)$ is independent of X , and the density function of ϵ is symmetric about 0 and non-increasing on $[0, \infty)$

In this setup, J. Lei and Wasserman (2014) prove that there exists another representation of our optimal oracle prediction band from (3), which does not involve conditional quantile functions, but takes the simple form

$$(6) \quad \mathcal{C}_{hom}^*(X_{n+1}) = \left[\mu(X_{n+1}) - q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|}, \mu(X_{n+1}) + q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|} \right]$$

where $q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|}$ is the $(1 - \alpha)$ -quantile of the distribution of absolute residuals (the noise variable). In particular, they show optimality in the following sense:

1. \mathcal{C}_{hom}^* has valid conditional coverage as specified in (2)
2. \mathcal{C}_{hom}^* has the shortest length among all bands with conditional coverage
3. \mathcal{C}_{hom}^* has the shortest average length among all bands with marginal coverage

This conditional mean-based oracle representation, when put into perspective from our conformal framework, motivates the application of the score function we have already seen in Example 2. This score function is also based on conditional means, and the induced split nonconformity scores generate a prediction band, \mathcal{C}_{split}^{mb} , which bears a striking resemblance to the oracle, \mathcal{C}_{hom}^* . This can be seen by plugging the mean-based scores from Example 2 into (5)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}_{split}^{mb}(X_{n+1}) &= \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R} : \tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, y)} \leq V_{(k)} \right\} \\ &= \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R} : |y - \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_{n+1})| \leq V_{(k)} \right\} \\ &= \left\{ y \in \left[\hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_{n+1}) - V_{(k)}, \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_{n+1}) + V_{(k)} \right] \right\} \end{aligned}$$

At first this might seem like a simple plug-in estimate for the oracle, however note that we do not use a naive estimate for $q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|}$, such as the $(1 - \alpha)$ -quantile of the empirical distribution of fitted absolute residuals. Instead, we have introduced a conformalized version of this quantile, as captured in $V_{(k)}$, the k -th order statistic of the set $\{|Y_i - \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_i)|, i \in \mathcal{I}_2\}$. Thus, marginal coverage of \mathcal{C}_{split}^{mb} follows by Theorem 2.

For the step towards asymptotic efficiency of \mathcal{C}_{split}^{mb} (including conditional coverage), we need the convergence of \mathcal{C}_{split}^{mb} to \mathcal{C}_{hom}^* . This requires one more assumption on our estimator $\hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}$:

A3 (Consistency of base estimator) For n large enough,

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\mathbb{E}_X [(\hat{\mu}_n(X) - \mu(X))^2 \mid \hat{\mu}_n] \geq \eta_n \right) \leq \rho_n$$

for some sequences satisfying $\eta_n = o(1)$, $\rho_n = o(1)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

This is weaker than directly requiring $\mathbb{E}[(\hat{\mu}_n(X) - \mu(X))^2] = o(1)$. Given these assumptions, J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018) prove the following convergence result

Theorem 3 (Theorem 3.4 in J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018)). *Under Assumptions (A1), (A2), (A3), assuming in addition that $|Y - \mu(X)|$ has density bounded away from zero in an open neighborhood of its α -upper quantile, the split conformal band \mathcal{C}_{split}^{mb} satisfies*

$$\begin{aligned} & \lambda \left(\mathcal{C}_{n,split}^{mb}(X) \triangle \mathcal{C}_{hom}^*(X) \right) \\ = & \lambda \left([a_{n,X}, b_{n,X}] \triangle [a_X^*, b_X^*] \right) = o_p(1) \end{aligned}$$

where $\lambda(A)$ denotes the Lebesgue measure of a set A , $A \triangle B$ is the symmetric difference between sets A, B , and

$$\begin{aligned} [a_{n,X}, b_{n,X}] & \equiv [\hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X) - V_{(k)}, \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X) + V_{(k)}] \\ [a_X^*, b_X^*] & \equiv [\mu(X) - q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|}, \mu(X) + q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|}] \end{aligned}$$

For a full proof I refer the reader to Appendix A.2 in J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018). Note however, that the basic idea is simple: As is visible in the extended notation above for the sets $\mathcal{C}_{n,split}^{mb}(X)$ and $\mathcal{C}^*(X)$, we are basically dealing with the Lebesgue measure of a disjoint union (i.e. the symmetric difference) of intervals in \mathbb{R} . Given a partial overlap of $\mathcal{C}_{n,split}^{mb}(X)$ and $\mathcal{C}^*(X)$ for n large enough, the proof reduces to showing that $a_{n,X} - a_X^* = o_p(1)$ and $b_{n,X} - b_X^* = o_p(1)$. For this to happen, it suffices to show that $\hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X) - \mu(X) = o_p(1)$ and $V_{(k)} - q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|} = o_p(1)$. While convergence of the former follows almost immediately by Markov's inequality and (A3), convergence of the conformal quantiles $V_{(k)}$ requires a little more care. Note that an analogous result holds for the corresponding full conformal prediction band (from Example 1) and can be found in Theorem 3.5 in J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018). Thus, due to the optimality of the oracle \mathcal{C}_{hom}^* in this context, under the additional consistency of $\hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}$, our prediction band \mathcal{C}_{split}^{mb} achieves optimal length and location (conditional coverage) asymptotically.

3.4.2 Locally-weighted scores

The restrictions from the previous chapter can be too strict in some situations to capture the full complexity of the underlying data generating process. In particular, we could be interested in making conformal prediction adaptive to heteroskedascity, while maintaining the use of conditional mean estimates for our scores. It should make sense intuitively that the simple procedure \mathcal{C}_{split}^{mb} and the corresponding oracle \mathcal{C}_{hom}^* do not achieve the optimality properties in an heteroskedastic environment, since they generate intervals of constant length, by construction. Heteroskedascity however, implies that the conditional quantiles in the generalized oracle from (3),

$$\mathcal{C}^*(X_{n+1}) = [q_{\frac{\alpha}{2}}(X_{n+1}), q_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}(X_{n+1})],$$

can vary with $X_{n+1} = x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, such that we expect non-constant optimal interval lengths.

With that in mind, J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018) suggest a different score function for their split nonconformity scores and generate those through fitted residuals that are inversely scaled by a measure of their dispersion, that is

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{V}_i &= \frac{|Y_i - \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_i)|}{\hat{\rho}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_i)}, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}_2 \\ \tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(x,y)} &= \frac{|y - \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(x)|}{\hat{\rho}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(x)}\end{aligned}$$

where in this case, $\hat{\rho}_{\mathcal{I}_1}$ is an estimate of $\rho(x) = \mathbb{E}[|Y - \mu(X)| \mid X = x]$, and both $\hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}$ and $\hat{\rho}_{\mathcal{I}_1}$ are fitted only on the training set \mathcal{I}_1 .¹⁷ A straightforward approach estimates $\hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}$ in a first step, and consequently learns $\hat{\rho}_{\mathcal{I}_1}$ on the set of fitted absolute residuals, even though a joint estimation is also possible. By plugging these new scores into $\mathcal{C}_{split}(X_{n+1})$ from (5), we derive the interval shape

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}_{split}^{wmb}(X_{n+1}) &= \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R} : \tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1},y)} \leq V_{(k)} \right\} \\ &= \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R} : \frac{|y - \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_{n+1})|}{\hat{\rho}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_{n+1})} \leq V_{(k)} \right\} \\ &= \left\{ y \in [\hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_{n+1}) - \hat{\rho}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_{n+1}) \cdot V_{(k)}, \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_{n+1}) + \hat{\rho}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_{n+1}) \cdot V_{(k)}] \right\}\end{aligned}$$

Due to the symmetry of the weighted score function, Theorem 2 applies and we again obtain finite sample marginal coverage.¹⁸ Even though the procedure is meant to be adaptive to heteroscedasticity, there is no asymptotic guarantee for this approach to achieve exact conditional coverage and optimal length in an heteroskedastic setting, even though simulations in Chapter 3.5 indicate that this ad hoc strategy often generalizes well in finite samples compared to its competitors. On the other hand, a clear advantage

¹⁷Again, only the split-conformal variant of the modified nonconformity scores is given, however a full conformal analogue can be obtained analogously.

¹⁸For details on the construction see Algorithm 3 in Appendix E.

of this procedure is that there are plenty of conditional mean estimators available, such that we can adapt our base learner flexibly according to the data generating process, for example by comparing generalization errors on unseen data.

3.4.3 Conformalized quantile regression

The locally-weighted conformal prediction intervals have several drawbacks. First of all, as noted in J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018), when situated in an homoscedastic setting the method suffers from inflated interval lengths compared to the standard mean based split conformal ones (\mathcal{C}_{split}^{mb}). The authors argue that this is presumably due to the extra variability introduced by estimating both μ and ρ . Secondly, as noted in Romano, Patterson, and Candes (2019), the weighted procedure can systematically underestimate the residual variation, since it uses the estimated residuals generated on the set \mathcal{I}_1 to fit $\hat{\rho}_{\mathcal{I}_1}$, which in turn forces the correction term $V_{(k)}$ to be large and the intervals to be less adaptive than they could be. Additionally and as indicated before, we have no asymptotic efficiency property of weighted intervals similar to the one from Theorem 3, but with respect to the general oracle from (3).

Against this backdrop, Romano, Patterson, and Candes (2019) suggest an alternative approach, named *conformalized quantile regression*. Instead of relying on any kind of conditional mean estimator, the split nonconformity scores are generated from a score function that incorporates quantile regression estimates; to be specific they take the form

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{V}_i &= \max \{ \hat{q}_{\alpha/2}(X_i) - Y_i, Y_i - \hat{q}_{1-\alpha/2}(X_i) \}, \quad i \in \mathcal{I}_2 \\ \tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(x,y)} &= \max \{ \hat{q}_{\alpha/2}(x) - y, y - \hat{q}_{1-\alpha/2}(x) \},\end{aligned}$$

where $\hat{q}_{\alpha/2}$ and $\hat{q}_{1-\alpha/2}$ are two conditional quantile functions that have been previously fitted on the training set \mathcal{I}_1 , given a suitable quantile regression algorithm \mathcal{A} .¹⁹ We can derive the final prediction intervals as given in Romano, Patterson, and Candes (2019) by plugging these nonconformity scores into $\mathcal{C}_{split}(X_{n+1})$ from (5),

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}_{split}^{qb}(X_{n+1}) &= \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R} : \tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1},y)} \leq V_{(k)} \right\} \\ &= \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R} : \max \left(\hat{q}_{\alpha/2}(X_{n+1}) - y, y - \hat{q}_{1-\alpha/2}(X_{n+1}) \right) \leq V_{(k)} \right\} \\ &= \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R} : \left(\hat{q}_{\alpha/2}(X_{n+1}) - y \leq V_{(k)} \right) \wedge \left(y - \hat{q}_{1-\alpha/2}(X_{n+1}) \leq V_{(k)} \right) \right\} \\ &= \left\{ y \in \mathbb{R} : \left(\hat{q}_{\alpha/2}(X_{n+1}) - V_{(k)} \leq y \right) \wedge \left(y \leq \hat{q}_{1-\alpha/2}(X_{n+1}) + V_{(k)} \right) \right\} \\ &= \left\{ y \in \left[\hat{q}_{\alpha/2}(X_{n+1}) - V_{(k)}, \hat{q}_{1-\alpha/2}(X_{n+1}) + V_{(k)} \right] \right\}\end{aligned}$$

¹⁹I consider only the split version of the nonconformity scores, however a full conformal version can be characterized analogously.

where as usual $k = \lceil (1 - \alpha)(|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1) \rceil$, and $V_{(k)}$ is the k -th order statistic of the set $\{\tilde{V}_i : i \in \mathcal{I}_2\}$. For the intuition behind this construction, I refer to Romano, Patterson, and Candès (2019). Once again, we can apply Theorem 2 to achieve the finite sample marginal coverage guarantee.

In simulations, Romano, Patterson, and Candès (2019) compare their method (\mathcal{C}_{split}^{qb}) with the mean-based (\mathcal{C}_{split}^{mb}) and locally-weighted ($\mathcal{C}_{split}^{wmb}$) one, across different base estimators and 11 datasets. In short, locally-weighted intervals generally outperform mean-based conformal intervals, and conformalized quantile regression outperforms both (by varying margins).²⁰

This can of course be due to a favourable selection of datasets and the focus on unconditional averages. However, as shown in Sesia and Candès (2020) and in contrast to the locally-weighted intervals, conformalized quantile regression exhibits a theoretical justification for large samples and under regularity conditions, which generalizes the asymptotic result from the homoscedastic setting: The quantile based prediction intervals can provide optimal asymptotic conditional coverage in a similar fashion as the one in Theorem 3, but with respect to the general oracle

$$\mathcal{C}^*(X_{n+1}) = [q_{\alpha/2}(X_{n+1}), q_{1-\alpha/2}(X_{n+1})].$$

Recall that \mathcal{C}^* is by construction, and universally, the narrowest symmetric prediction interval that has valid conditional coverage. Sesia and Candès (2020) show in their Theorem 1 that for *i.i.d.* data, if a condition similar to (A3), but weaker than requiring $\hat{q}_{\alpha/2} \xrightarrow{L^2} q_{\alpha/2}$ and $\hat{q}_{1-\alpha/2} \xrightarrow{L^2} q_{1-\alpha/2}$ holds, then we achieve

$$\lambda \left(\mathcal{C}_{split}^{qb}(X) \triangle \mathcal{C}^*(X) \right) = o_p(1).$$

In their work Romano, Patterson, and Candès (2019) note that the estimation of quantile regression estimators can often be casted as an optimization problem with “pinball loss” function, a formulation whose generality makes the method in principle widely applicable and enables leveraging a variety of machine learning methods to learn q_α . Unfortunately, as opposed to the estimation of conditional means, at this point of time there do not exist many production ready frameworks that implement this loss function as a standard, which could in practise hinder the adoption of the procedure. For this reason and others, it can in practise often be more difficult to generate accurate estimates for conditional quantiles than for conditional means, especially in complex data settings.

²⁰Performance was measured in terms of average (i.e. marginal) coverage and average length of the respective prediction intervals. Thus, conditional coverage measures were neglected by the authors.

Still, when taking into account some additional practical considerations²¹, conformalized quantile regression constitutes one of the most promising candidates in the field.

3.4.4 Distributional conformal prediction

The last contribution from the literature of conformal prediction in regression settings considered here is by Chernozhukov, Wüthrich, and Zhu (2019). The authors motivate their idea by the observation that all approaches from before make use of deviations in their score functions which are measured in absolute levels, which can be suboptimal in certain situations; in contrast, their idea is to consider ranks of random variables that have been scaled into the interval $(0, 1)$ by the probability integral transform, given an initial estimate of the conditional cumulative distribution function (CDF), $F_{Y|X}(y|x)$. A full description would take too much space, therefore I refer to Algorithm 5 for the essential steps, and Chapter 2 in Chernozhukov, Wüthrich, and Zhu (2019) for details. As before, the finite sample marginal coverage in (1) holds by Theorem 2; further, the authors provide a result regarding asymptotic conditional coverage (see Theorem 3 in their paper). This conditional property, however, follows only if the estimated conditional CDF, \hat{f}_n , is a consistent estimator of the true $F_{Y|X}$. Thus, for finite samples the accuracy of this estimate decides how close we approximate conditional validity. For completeness, this method is also considered in the following simulation.

3.5 Empirical comparison of conformal methods

To this day, most existing simulations in the conformal inference literature focus on performance measures such as average interval length- and coverage (e.g. J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018), Romano, Patterson, and Candes (2019)). This comes natural, since the main result of conformal procedures is the finite sample marginal (or average) coverage guarantee. Additionally, these metrics are easily computable for both artificially generated data as well as real datasets. However, as we witness the emergence of new asymptotic results and alternative conformal procedures, it can be of considerable interest to explore how the numerous competitors perform in terms of conditional coverage and conditional interval length. Of particular empirical interest is the combination of heteroskedastic noise and finite samples, since on the one hand the optimal length of intervals varies across regressor values, and on the other hand asymptotic conditional coverage cannot be assured.

Therefore, this first part of the simulations compares the previously discussed conformal methods in a heteroscedastic regression setting across qualitatively different data generating processes (DGPs) that have been established in the recent literature. I implement

²¹Quantile regression is often too conservative, especially when employing the quantile regression forests from Meinshausen and Ridgeway (2006), which results in unnecessarily wide prediction intervals. As noted by Romano, Patterson, and Candes (2019), one can mitigate this problem by tuning the nominal quantiles of the underlying method as additional hyperparameters in cross validation. While this tuning does not invalidate the marginal coverage guarantee, it may yield shorter intervals.

the split-version of each procedure, making use of the insight from J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018) that split conformal intervals exhibit a clear computational advantage compared to the full conformal ones, with similar performance in average length and coverage.

The methods under consideration are

- M1** Mean-based split conformal method (\mathcal{C}_{split}^{mb}) as in Algorithm 2
- M2** Locally-weighted split conformal method ($\mathcal{C}_{split}^{wmb}$) as in Algorithm 3
- M3** Conformalized quantile regression (\mathcal{C}_{split}^{qb}) as in Algorithm 4
- M4** Distributional conformal prediction ($\mathcal{C}_{split}^{cdf}$) as in Algorithm 5
- M5** The generalized oracle from (3)

It is clear at this point that the mean-based split conformal method is not tailored to this setting, however it can be considered a point of reference, in addition to the generalized oracle, which guarantees conditional coverage and optimal length. In the implementation, I use random forests from Pedregosa et al. (2011) as base learners for the first two mean-based methods, and quantile regression trees from Meinshausen and Ridgeway (2006) for the third and fourth procedure.²² This choice was made due to reasons of comparability across methods and the relative stability of random forests concerning tuning parameters, in addition to their good performance in many settings. While the details on the DGPs can be found in Appendix D.1, qualitatively they can be summarized as follows:

- DGP1** Particularly simple with linear mean $\mu(x)$; heteroskedastic, normally distributed errors; univariate regressor matrix, as found in Chernozhukov, Wüthrich, and Zhu (2019)
- DGP2** Stochastic, non-linear mean; heteroskedastic errors with rare, large outliers; univariate regressor matrix, as found in Romano, Patterson, and Candes (2019)
- DGP3** Linear mean $\mu(x)$; heteroskedastic, heavy-tailed errors; correlated regressors $X_i(1), \dots, X_i(10)$, sparse setting, as found similarly in J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018)
- DGP4** Non-linear mean $\mu(x)$; heteroskedastic errors; independent regressors $X_i(1), \dots, X_i(100)$; sparse setting, as found in Kivaranovic, Johnson, and Leeb (2020)

Average results. Before we have a look on the conditional metrics, I will shortly discuss the average (marginal) results across methods. As expected and visible in Table 3, all candidates maintain nominal marginal coverage across all DGPs.²³ Additionally, at least

²²Since distributional conformal prediction requires the estimation of conditional CDFs, I have used quantile regression trees and subsequently numerical integration in the fitting step. For a discussion on how quantile regression or, alternatively, distribution regression can be used for that purpose, see Appendix B in Chernozhukov, Wüthrich, and Zhu (2019).

²³I set $\alpha = 0.1$, a value commonly found in the conformal literature.

on average, no method can consistently outperform the naive mean-based approach (M1) in terms of average lengths²⁴. However, given the realistic sample size of $n = 1,000$, the procedures (M1) - (M3) often approximate the optimal average length of the oracle well, with the exception of DGP4. In contrast, (M4) seems to underperform in most setups in terms of average length.

Conditional results. This leads to the more interesting question of whether the procedures can also maintain coverage conditionally on each $X = x$, and how the conditional length adapts. While it is straightforward to plot kernel regression estimates²⁵ of conditional length and conditional coverage on the regressor variable for DGP1 and DGP2 (univariate case), for the two latter DGPs I decided to plot the two metrics on $\beta^T x$ instead, which can be justified as an appropriate summary statistic in the multivariate setup, by inspection of the DGP’s internal structure. This yields two plots for each DGP, which can be found in Figures 1-4 in Appendix C. In addition to kernel regression estimates for each of the four methods, the left hand panel in each figure always includes a dotted curve for the conditional length of the oracle band (M5). On the right hand side of each figure there are kernel regression estimates of the conditional coverage for each method, and another dotted curve that illustrates the conditional variance, $\mathbb{V}(Y | X = x)$ (scale on secondary y -axis). As expected, the length of the mean-based intervals (M1) does not adapt at all to different realisations of the covariate vector, yielding a constant in the left plot and an excess (deficit) in conditional coverage for small (large) values of $\mathbb{V}(Y | X = x)$ in the right plot, across all DGPs. With respect to the conditional length panels, it seems as if the locally-weighted mean-based approach (M2) and the quantile regression approach (M3) approximate the oracle the closest, with the exception of DGP 4, where all methods fail. The CDF-based approach (M4) is also often capable to fit the correct functional shape of conditional lengths, but generates larger widths, a fact which has already been apparent in the marginal results. It is evident that for the DGPs where the base-learners (trees) are able to learn the true functional form sufficiently well (either a conditional mean, the conditional quantiles, or the CDF), the kernel estimates for the conditional length also approximate the true oracle curve well.²⁶ Therefore, the non-linear mean in DGP4, even with $n = 5,000$, poses a real challenge for the procedures; it however appears as if the weighted mean-based approach has a slight advantage, since learning the conditional mean seems easier than the conditional quantiles.

Corresponding to these observations, the right panels on the conditional coverage comple-

²⁴If we leave out the highly challenging DGP4, then (M3), i.e. the quantile based approach seems to have a small edge on average.

²⁵I have used the implementation in Seabold and Perktold (2010) for nonparametric kernel regression. Consequently, the optimal bandwidth for each estimate was tuned internally, which in some cases generates kernel regression surfaces which seem a bit volatile. One could explore a manual tuning of the bandwidth in future work.

²⁶This is suggested by additional calculations of the mean-squared errors on hold-out data for each DGP and method. Note that this is in line with results from J. Lei, G’Sell, et al. (2018) which conclude that interval lengths are highly (positively) correlated with test errors for a given regression estimator in the mean-based setup.

ment the impression: Apart from DGP4, all procedures improve on the conditional level compared to the naive mean-based approach (M1). The amount of improvement is rather larger for the first two DGPs, with almost nominal coverage across covariate space (neglecting boundary effects introduced by the kernel estimate). For DGP3, all procedures struggle in regions of very large variance (the boundaries), although even there considerable improvement is visible compared to the mean-based baseline. Again, DGP4 is an example where procedures break down. All empirical results are however in line with the theoretical predictions, which only guarantee conditional coverage and oracle length in the limit and under consistency assumptions (the asymptotic statements under heteroscedasticity hold only for methods M3 and M4). It is an interesting finding that overall, the ad hoc approach M2 seems to work quite well in comparison to the theoretically justified methods.

4 Conformal inference for individual treatment effects

4.1 Potential outcome framework

Suppose we are in the potential outcome framework (Rubin (1974)) with a binary treatment, i.e. consider the treatment variable

$$W_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if unit } i \text{ is in the treatment group} \\ 0, & \text{if unit } i \text{ is in the control group} \end{cases}$$

and the pair of *potential outcomes* $(Y_i(1), Y_i(0))$, where $Y_i(1)$ is the outcome that would have been observed if $W_i = 1$, and $Y_i(0)$ is the outcome that would have been observed if $W_i = 0$. Suppose further that for each unit we observe a vector of covariates X_i , the actual outcome Y_i , and in total collect a sample of n units. This gives us a collection of n random vectors, which we assume to be *i.i.d.* over some joint distribution P on $(Y, W, X, Y(1), Y(0)) \in (\mathbb{R} \times \{0, 1\} \times \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R})$, i.e.

$$(Y_i, W_i, X_i, Y_i(1), Y_i(0))_{i=1}^n \stackrel{i.i.d.}{\sim} P$$

By using the *stable unit treatment value assumption* (SUTVA), we can write the observed outcome as

$$(7) \quad Y_i = W_i \cdot Y_i(1) + (1 - W_i) \cdot Y_i(0)$$

providing a closer link between the observed dataset $\mathcal{D}_n = (Y_i, W_i, X_i)_{i=1}^n$ and the theoretical distribution $(Y, W, X, Y(1), Y(0)) \sim P$.

We are interested in inference on the *individual treatment effect* (ITE) for an out-of-sample unit $n + 1$, defined as

$$(8) \quad \Delta_{n+1} \equiv Y_{n+1}(1) - Y_{n+1}(0)$$

Maybe due to the seemingly inaccessibility of the ITE (in the spirit of the fundamental problem of causal inference), researchers have in recent years placed emphasis on the estimation of the conditional average treatment effect function (CATE), defined as

$$\tau(x) \equiv \mathbb{E}[Y(1) - Y(0) \mid X = x]$$

Estimation of the CATE can be done flexibly through a variety of algorithms, but even though some of those enjoy theoretical appeal in terms of consistency and convergence rates, they generally perform poorly in terms of uncertainty quantification.

As documented by Dorie et al. (2019) and Hahn, Dorie, and Murray (2019), a general observation from empirical studies and data challenges has been that while many of the point estimators for the CATE perform well with regard to metrics such as the root-mean-squared error or the bias, nominal coverage of induced confidence intervals is rarely achieved by any procedure. Even the methods in Chapter 2 that provide an asymptotic coverage result on confidence intervals (e.g. Wager and Athey (2018)), typically fail to maintain nominal coverage in finite samples. Since drawing reliable confidence bands from finite samples around estimates of possibly high-dimensional regression functions is naturally a delicate endeavour, some authors such as Chernozhukov, Demirer, et al. (2018) focus on simpler features of $\tau(x)$, e.g. its best linear predictor. Switching to this simpler estimand avoids some of the strong assumptions that one usually needs on the underlying estimators, and can enable more reliable confidence statements. However, it also yields a worse approximation to the true individual treatment effect function, and neglects the inherent variability in the response.

Therefore, instead of looking at confidence intervals for the non-random function $\tau(x)$ (at each $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$), or simpler features thereof, we can employ techniques from the conformal inference literature to construct prediction intervals for the ITE, Δ_{n+1} . As noted in the introduction, developing such an interval estimator automatically takes the inherent variability in the response into account (the part of it not explained by the regressors) and as we will see, enables valid inference for generic machine learning algorithms, without any assumption other than that of operating on *i.i.d.* samples, at least when situated in a randomized controlled trial.

4.2 Counterfactual inference

The major challenge that we face in the process of constructing prediction intervals on Δ_{n+1} is the fact that any estimator that depends on the joint distribution of $(Y(0), Y(1))$ is

infeasible, since we can never observe joint outcomes. Additionally, all the nonconformity scores we have seen in previous chapters involve some measure of distance between the variable of interest and a model that was generated from the observed data. Again, this strategy is not directly applicable here, since Δ_{n+1} is never observed.

Therefore, all the concepts that I will present in the following generate prediction intervals for the counterfactuals $Y(1)$ and $Y(0)$ separately, which can then be combined for inference on Δ_{n+1} . In a first step, the primary objects of inference are thus the intervals C_1, C_0 which depend on the location in covariate space, and obey

$$(9) \quad \mathbb{P}(Y_{n+1}(w) \in C_w(X_{n+1})) \geq 1 - \alpha \quad (w = 0, 1)$$

for a pre-specified level α . Let us exemplarily focus on C_1 for a moment. By (7), our observed data is only suitable for inference on $Y(1)$ conditionally on having received treatment, i.e. the data we will use to construct C_1 will come from the *sampling distribution*

$$\{(X_i, Y_i) | W_i = 1\} \stackrel{i.i.d.}{\sim} P_{X,Y|W=1} = P_{X|W=1} \times P_{Y|X,W=1} = P_{X|W=1} \times P_{Y(1)|X}$$

where the last equality in distributions comes from the *unconfoundedness* assumption²⁷, which is a minimal requirement I will make in the following,

$$\{Y(1), Y(0)\} \perp\!\!\!\perp W \mid X$$

Recall at this point that standard conformal inference as we have seen so far requires the sequence of observed data to be exchangeable with the new draw for which our prediction interval shall hold coverage. This implies that by naively applying conformal inference procedures to the treated units, we can only build a prediction band for new draws generated from

$$\{(X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1}) | W_{n+1} = 1\} \sim P_{X,Y|W=1} = P_{X|W=1} \times P_{Y(1)|X} = P_{X,Y(1)|W=1}.$$

An analogous argument holds for the control units. We will name the induced conditional intervals *W-conditional* conformal intervals²⁸, which by the above argument are constructed to satisfy

$$(10) \quad \mathbb{P}(Y_{n+1}(w) \in C_w(X_{n+1}) | W_{n+1} = w) \geq 1 - \alpha \quad (w = 0, 1)$$

²⁷See Rosenbaum and Rubin (1983) for details and a discussion of this assumption.

²⁸Note that the conformal method is designed to satisfy *marginal coverage*. Fortunately, by applying the conformal method “conditional” on any event with positive probability, the marginal coverage guarantee extends to conditional coverage on $W = 1$ and $W = 0$. This is not the same as the conditional coverage in (2), where we conditioned on events of probability zero. For a formal proof of concept I refer to Chapter 3 in Kivaranovic, Ristl, et al. (2020).

These prediction bands are obviously in general not equal to (9), which are based on a *target distribution* of our new draw which obeys

$$\{(X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1}(w))\} \sim P_{X,Y(w)} = P_X \times P_{Y(w)|X} \quad (w = 0, 1)$$

In the setting of completely randomized controlled trials, on which I will limit the attention in the rest of this thesis, the discrepancy between (9) and (10) is resolved by assumption: Complete randomization implies $W \perp\!\!\!\perp X$, $\{Y(1), Y(0)\} \perp\!\!\!\perp W$, and $W \perp\!\!\!\perp \mathcal{D}_n$, which yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{P}(Y_{n+1}(w) \in C_w(X_{n+1})) \\ &= \mathbb{P}(Y_{n+1}(w) \in C_w(X_{n+1}) | W_{n+1} = w) \quad (w = 0, 1) \end{aligned}$$

Note that this setting implies that we can use any of the conformal methods mentioned in previous chapters to construct W -conditional conformal intervals, which then automatically coincide with our objects of interest, C_1, C_0 .

It is worth mentioning that counterfactual inference as in (9) can also be achieved in observational studies (under SUTVA, unconfoundedness, and an additional overlap assumption) through results on weighted conformal inference which have recently been developed by Tibshirani and Foygel (2019) in a regression setting, and applied to the potential outcome framework by L. Lei and Candès (2020). These advanced methods still construct counterfactual intervals C_1, C_0 separately in the treated and control subsets, but make use of a reweighting scheme. By reweighting each observation by an estimate of its propensity score $e(x) = \mathbb{P}(W = 1 | X = x)$, the procedure can, under regularity conditions, account for the difference between the observed *sampling distribution*, and the *target distribution* of a new draw.

4.3 Inference on the ITE

Operating under the assumptions of a randomized controlled trial (RCT), I will now describe two strategies to construct prediction intervals for Δ_{n+1} based on our counterfactual intervals from (9). The strategies differ in the strength of underlying assumptions, as well as the scope of their coverage guarantee.

Simple procedure: Let us assume C_1, C_0 are both constructed at level $1 - \frac{\alpha}{2}$ and in interval form²⁹ which yields the representation

$$(11) \quad C_w(X_{n+1}) = [l_w(X_{n+1}), u_w(X_{n+1})] \quad (w = 0, 1)$$

²⁹Otherwise simply take the supremum and infimum of the prediction sets to generate corresponding intervals.

A straightforward approach for a prediction interval on Δ_{n+1} is to simply set

$$(12) \quad C_{\Delta}(X_{n+1}) \equiv [l_1(X_{n+1}) - u_0(X_{n+1}), u_1(X_{n+1}) - l_0(X_{n+1})]$$

The coverage guarantee of this interval is then directly inherited from the marginal coverage of the counterfactual intervals through the set inclusion,

$$(13) \quad \begin{aligned} & \{Y_{n+1}(1) \in [l_1(X_{n+1}), u_1(X_{n+1})]\} \cap \{Y_{n+1}(0) \in [l_0(X_{n+1}), u_0(X_{n+1})]\} \\ & \subset \{\Delta_{n+1} \in C_{\Delta}(X_{n+1})\} \end{aligned}$$

The proof of level $1 - \alpha$ marginal coverage of C_{Δ} then basically follows by the Bonferroni type inequality

$$\mathbb{P}(A \cap B) \geq \mathbb{P}(A) + \mathbb{P}(B) - 1$$

Theorem 4 (Theorem 1 in Kivaranovic, Ristl, et al. (2020)). *In the setting of a randomized controlled trial, given the two W -conditional prediction intervals from (10), both at level $1 - \frac{\alpha}{2}$, and $C_{\Delta}(X_{n+1})$ as defined in (12), we have that*

$$\mathbb{P}(\Delta_{n+1} \in C_{\Delta}(X_{n+1})) \geq 1 - \alpha$$

That is, C_{Δ} is a valid, finite sample prediction interval with marginal coverage for the ITE at level $1 - \alpha$.

I have taken note that this idea has recently been explored by Kivaranovic, Ristl, et al. (2020), who also sketch a proof thereof in their Appendix A. In the light of the asymptotic results from Chapter 3, note that an *asymptotic conditional coverage* of C_1 and C_0 carries over to C_{Δ} in a similar way as the marginal coverage in Theorem 4, while asymptotic optimal length cannot be assured.

Asymptotic procedure: The second construction works via the decomposition of the response into

$$\begin{aligned} Y &= \mathbb{E}[Y | X, W] + \epsilon_{X,W} \\ &= f(X, W) + \epsilon_{X,W}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\epsilon_{X,W} = Y - \mathbb{E}[Y | X, W]$, and since being in an RCT, $X \perp\!\!\!\perp W$. Then, we can state the following,

Theorem 5 (Theorem 3 in Kivaranovic, Ristl, et al. (2020)). *In the setting of a randomized controlled trial, let f_n be a consistent estimator of f .³⁰ Consider the two W -*

³⁰In this context, consistency is defined by Kivaranovic, Ristl, et al. (2020) as follows: For all compact $K \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ and for all $\epsilon > 0$, we have

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\sup_{(x,w) \in K \times \{0,1\}} |f_n(x, w) - f(x, w)| < \epsilon \right) \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 1.$$

conditional conformal prediction intervals from (10) both at level $1 - \alpha$, and suppose that

$$\mathbb{P}(l_w(X_{n+1}) \leq f_n(X_{n+1}, w) \leq u_w(X_{n+1})) = 1, \quad w \in \{0, 1\}$$

where $l_w(X_{n+1})$ and $u_w(X_{n+1})$ are the upper- and lower interval bounds of the counterfactuals from (11). Assume further that $(\epsilon_{X,W=1}, \epsilon_{X,W=0} | X) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma)$, with equal variances and non-negative covariances. Set the modified interval bounds for the counterfactuals as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{l}_w(X_{n+1}) &\equiv f_n(X_{n+1}, w) - \frac{f_n(X_{n+1}, w) - l_w(X_{n+1})}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \tilde{u}_w(X_{n+1}) &\equiv f_n(X_{n+1}, w) + \frac{u_w(X_{n+1}) - f_n(X_{n+1}, w)}{\sqrt{2}} \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\tilde{C}_\Delta(X_{n+1}) \equiv \left[\tilde{l}_1(X_{n+1}) - \tilde{u}_0(X_{n+1}), \tilde{u}_1(X_{n+1}) - \tilde{l}_0(X_{n+1}) \right]$$

is a prediction interval with asymptotic marginal coverage for Δ_{n+1} at level $1 - \alpha$, i.e.

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{P}\left(\Delta_{n+1} \in \tilde{C}_\Delta(X_{n+1})\right) \geq 1 - \alpha.$$

A proof can be found in Appendix A of Kivaranovic, Ristl, et al. (2020). This prediction band needs much stronger assumptions than the simple procedure, and is only asymptotically valid (if the assumptions hold). However, the hope is that in many cases gaussian errors constitute a realistic approximation to reality, and that given a large array of machine learning methods, the true f can be learned accurately enough. In this case, one would suspect the method to generate narrower intervals than the simple procedure and in consequence to be more powerful.³¹

Finally, an argument could be made that the asymptotic procedure is not in the spirit of conformal prediction (no finite sample guarantee), and that we could therefore abandon the conformal parts in our construction of prediction bands for the ITE altogether. To determine whether the use of conformal intervals in the asymptotic procedure brings any benefit *in finite samples*, compared to alternative non-conformal (but also asymptotic consistent) approaches, in the simulations I will also look at two naive variations of the simple- and asymptotic procedures from above:

- In the *first variant*, denoted as C'_Δ , we simply replace the level $(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2})$ W -conditional conformal intervals C_1, C_0 in the *simple procedure*, by naive level $(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2})$ prediction

³¹This intuition is confirmed in simulations by Kivaranovic, Ristl, et al. (2020), and supported by the power simulations at the end of this thesis.

intervals for the counterfactuals, which can be generated from methods such as quantile regression.³²

- In the *second variant*, denoted as \tilde{C}'_{Δ} , we analogously replace the level $(1 - \alpha)$ W -conditional conformal intervals in the *asymptotic procedure*, by naive prediction intervals for the counterfactuals, but this time at target level $1 - \alpha$.

A candidate for future work: In a recent publication L. Lei and Candès (2020) outline an additional candidate for inference on the ITE, although they refer to the environment of an observational study. Nevertheless, this alternative method, which they call the *nested approach*, extends to our framework, by passing the two W -conditional prediction intervals from (10) as its counterfactual input sets. The authors develop an *exact* version of the nested approach, which brings a marginal coverage guarantee but often performs worse empirically than even the simple method in terms of interval lengths (and performs similar in terms of coverage). Their alternative *inexact* version of the approach can in some cases yield drastically shorter intervals than the simple approach, but lacks any theoretical coverage guarantee. For these reasons I do not consider the nested approach. Nevertheless the inexact version could become an interesting subject of future research if conditions are developed that yield a theoretical underpinning.

4.4 Power considerations

While the simple- and asymptotic procedures from before control interval coverage in some form, the usefulness of these constructions naturally depends on power considerations, if we wish to make inferential claims on the ITE with confidence: For instance, one can decide to assign treatment to a patient if the lower (upper) prediction bound of her ITE interval is positive (negative), i.e. an effect different from zero is to expect. However, for prediction intervals there are some fundamental differences to traditional power analysis considerations. A typical power analysis in the potential outcome model could be interested in the minimum sample size that is required to detect a certain average treatment effect (ATE) size with a fixed power, or vice versa. Under the typical assumptions, and in particular in the randomized controlled trial setting, the ATE

$$(14) \quad ATE \equiv \mathbb{E}[Y(1)] - \mathbb{E}[Y(0)]$$

can be estimated by the difference in sample means between treatment- and control group. We can then use basic results from two sample t-tests to determine a minimum sample size, or use large sample normal approximations of this difference in means to construct a confidence interval \hat{C}_n^{ATE} for the true ATE. Obviously, for $n \rightarrow \infty$ the confidence region

³²In the simulation study we focus on a homoscedastic setting, such that in reality I employ an even simpler strategy than quantile regression, which in this setting converges to the same limit (that is (6)). Details can be found in Appendix G.

around the ATE shrinks to zero and we can detect any effect size of this parameter (whose absolute value is positive) with power 1, i.e.

$$1 - \beta_{ATE} \equiv \mathbb{P} \left(0 \notin \hat{C}_n^{ATE} \mid ATE \neq 0 \right) \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 1.$$

Motivated by the example of a new patient receiving treatment from above, we can similarly consider a notion of power for any type of prediction interval on the ITE,

$$(15) \quad 1 - \beta_{ITE} \equiv \mathbb{P} (0 \notin C_{ITE}(X_{n+1}) \mid \Delta_{n+1} \neq 0).$$

Unfortunately, since prediction intervals also incorporate the signal's inherent residual noise, even with $n \rightarrow \infty$ there is a lower bound on the detectable magnitude of the effect, that is some effect sizes of Δ_{n+1} are not detectable at all (power zero) even for some type of oracle procedure. It is therefore of interest to analyse which effect sizes are at least in principle detectable, for a given level α and power $1 - \beta_{ITE}$, if we replace C_{ITE} in (15) by a suitable oracle procedure on the one hand, and by our simple conformal prediction procedure from (12) on the other hand.³³ In particular, it would make sense to analyse the loss in power of our simple procedure compared to an oracle, which is not due to estimation error, but due to the construction itself. This is because the simple procedure works via the set inclusion in (13), which can render the induced intervals conservative by nature. Then, as soon as we have developed a sense for the loss in power which is induced by the simple procedure on top of an oracle, I will subsequently check in simulations whether the asymptotic procedure (and the variants $C'_\Delta, \tilde{C}'_\Delta$) is able to reduce this gap, and how its asymptotic coverage property is reflected in the empirical finite sample coverage.

However, it is rather difficult to make general statements about the power of an oracle or of our simple intervals C_Δ , since any claim highly depends on the distribution of the individual treatment effects, Δ_{n+1} . Therefore, before jumping straight into the simulations, it is worth to add some structure to our setup and derive some basic theoretical insights on that.

4.4.1 Theoretical insights

Let us in the following focus on a semiparametric model for the counterfactuals,³⁴

$$(16) \quad \begin{aligned} Y(1) &= m(X) + \tau(X) + \epsilon_1 \\ Y(0) &= m(X) + \epsilon_0 \end{aligned}$$

³³The asymptotic procedure will usually be somewhere between these extremes in terms of detectable effect sizes.

³⁴This choice of modeling was influenced by Robinson (1988) and has gained popularity in the recent literature about heterogeneous treatment effect estimation, both theoretically and for simulation purposes, see e.g. Wager and Athey (2018) and Nie and Wager (2021).

where $m(\cdot)$ is a function of varying complexity that will be called the *baseline main effect*, and $\tau(X)$ is the conditional average treatment effect (here not yet evaluated at $X = x$). This directly implies that

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_{n+1} &= \tau(X_{n+1}) + (\epsilon_{1,n+1} - \epsilon_{0,n+1}) \\ &= \tau(X_{n+1}) + \nu_{n+1}.\end{aligned}$$

Further, I wish to explicitly abstract from issues of heteroskedasticity at this point which have been investigated in Chapter 3.5. Therefore, we can without loss of asymptotic optimality utilize the mean-based split conformal method (Algorithm 2) to construct prediction bands for the counterfactuals, and subsequently generate prediction intervals for the ITE, as described before. In the case of our simple ITE procedure, this yields the following representation of the prediction set in (12), given the mean-based split procedure was used for the counterfactual intervals:

$$\begin{aligned}C_{\Delta}(X_{n+1}) &= [l_1(X_{n+1}) - u_0(X_{n+1}), u_1(X_{n+1}) - l_0(X_{n+1})] \\ &= \left[\hat{\mu}_1(X_{n+1}) - q_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\hat{\epsilon}_1|} - \hat{\mu}_0(X_{n+1}) - q_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\hat{\epsilon}_0|}, \hat{\mu}_1(X_{n+1}) + q_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\hat{\epsilon}_1|} - \hat{\mu}_0(X_{n+1}) + q_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\hat{\epsilon}_0|} \right]\end{aligned}$$

where $\hat{\mu}_1$ and $\hat{\mu}_0$ estimate $\mathbb{E}[Y | X = x, W = 1]$ and $\mathbb{E}[Y | X = x, W = 0]$, whereas $q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\hat{\epsilon}_1|}$ and $q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\hat{\epsilon}_0|}$ are the corresponding order statistics $V_{(k)}$ from Algorithm 2 represented as empirical quantiles. Therefore, in this context $q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\hat{\epsilon}_1|}$ stands for the $(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2})(\frac{1}{|Z_2|} + 1)$ -th empirical quantile of the residuals in the treatment group, based on conformalizing the residuals in a separate $\mathcal{I}_2 : \mathcal{I}_2 \subset \{\text{observation } i : i \text{ received treatment}\}$.

We can now compare two types of oracles: First of all, reconsider the representation of an oracle in an homoscedastic setting, as specified in (6), which for the target variable Δ_{n+1} takes the following form in this context,

$$(17) \quad \mathcal{C}_{fb}^*(X_{n+1}) = \left[\tau(X_{n+1}) - q_{1-\alpha}^{|\nu|}, \tau(X_{n+1}) + q_{1-\alpha}^{|\nu|} \right]$$

This oracle, however, completely bypasses the idea of constructing prediction bands for the two counterfactuals separately, and thus effectively avoids any conservativeness that is induced via our simple approach. Therefore, it makes sense to define another second-best oracle, which follows our procedure, but does not suffer from any estimation error in learning the conditional means and empirical quantiles. This second-best oracle can be written as follows

$$(18) \quad \mathcal{C}_{sb}^*(X_{n+1}) = \left[\tau(X_{n+1}) - q_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\epsilon_1|} - q_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\epsilon_0|}, \tau(X_{n+1}) + q_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\epsilon_1|} + q_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\epsilon_0|} \right]$$

The advantage to consider both oracles should be evident: The first oracle defines an optimal bound for any procedure that aims to construct prediction intervals for the ITE, while the second one explicitly targets our simple procedure. Thus, a comparison of those

two oracles gives an idea about the loss we induce through our conservative construction, which can then be compared to the remaining loss which is created on top of that by estimation error (when estimating C_Δ).

If we assume a continuous (absolute) error distribution (such that $\mathbb{P}(\Delta_{n+1} \neq 0) = 1$), then the event of the first-best oracle rightfully rejecting the null can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} & \{0 \notin \mathcal{C}_{fb}^*(X_{n+1}) \mid \Delta_{n+1} \neq 0\} \\ \iff & |\tau(X_{n+1})| \geq q_{1-\alpha}^{|\nu|} \end{aligned}$$

which implies that the power of this oracle depends on the distributions $F_{|\tau(X)|}$ and $F_{|\nu|}$ via the relation

$$(19) \quad 1 - \beta_{fb}^* \equiv \mathbb{P}_X(0 \notin \mathcal{C}_{fb}^*(X_{n+1}) \mid \Delta_{n+1} \neq 0) = 1 - F_{|\tau(X)|}(q_{1-\alpha}^{|\nu|})$$

An analogous argument yields that the the power of our second-best oracle depends on the distributions $F_{|\tau(X)|}$ and $(F_{|\epsilon_1|}, F_{|\epsilon_0|})$ via the relation

$$(20) \quad 1 - \beta_{sb}^* \equiv \mathbb{P}_X(0 \notin \mathcal{C}_{sb}^*(X_{n+1}) \mid \Delta_{n+1} \neq 0) = 1 - F_{|\tau(X)|}\left(q_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\epsilon_1|} + q_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\epsilon_0|}\right)$$

Let us first inspect the arguments in (19) and (20) at which we evaluate $F_{|\tau(X)|}$, namely $q_{1-\alpha}^{|\nu|}$ and $q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_1|} + q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_0|}$. For a fixed α , these values are completely determined by the residual distributions $F_{|\epsilon_1|}$, $F_{|\epsilon_0|}$, and $F_{|\nu|}$, which therefore make up the first channel through which our second-best oracle can lose power. That is, if $\mathcal{H}_\alpha \equiv \frac{q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_1|} + q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_0|}}{q_{1-\alpha}^{|\nu|}}$ is larger than one, we experience a loss in power introduced by our procedure, given that $F_{|\tau(X)|}$ puts positive probability on the region $\left[q_{1-\alpha}^{|\nu|}, q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_1|} + q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_0|}\right]$.³⁵ As simulation results in Table 4 suggest, for $\alpha = 0.1$, \mathcal{H}_α seems to be situated somewhere in (1.3, 1.9) for common symmetric error distributions. In fact, the results indicate that for some types of distributions, changing the residual variance does not have any impact on the measure \mathcal{H}_α . In the following, we will focus on $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_0 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, yielding a ratio $\mathcal{H}_{0.1} \approx 1.68$.³⁶

Upon inspecting the lengths of the second-best and first-best oracle intervals,³⁷ we note that their fraction, i.e. $\frac{l(\mathcal{C}_{sb}^*)}{l(\mathcal{C}_{fb}^*)}$, coincides with the ratio \mathcal{H}_α . If we take the relative length between the two oracles as our measure of performance, we can therefore say our simple procedure, C_Δ , can at best achieve ITE prediction intervals that are roughly 68% longer than the first-best oracle.

³⁵Note that as the argument of any cumulative distribution function goes to infinity, the value of the CDF converges to one, which would cause the power of either oracle to go to zero in this context.

³⁶For this main case of interest, i.e. $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_0 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, there is an additional plot in Figure 11 that shows how \mathcal{H}_α depends on α , which was fixed so far at $\alpha = 0.1$. This plot indicates that, at least for the normal case, the higher we set our α , the larger is our \mathcal{H}_α .

³⁷Note that the length of both oracles is constant across the covariate space, due to the simple construction via our mean-based conformal method.

This measure however, completely neglects the fact that power is influenced through a second channel, namely $F_{|\tau(X)|}$. It is true that the relative length between the oracles only depends on \mathcal{H}_α , but if $F_{|\tau(X)|}$ puts no probability on the region $\left[q_{1-\alpha}^{|\nu|}, q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_1|} + q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_0|} \right]$, then both oracles still yield the same power. In the next chapter's simulations, we generate $\tau(X)$ from different scale-families, i.e. $\tau(X) = s \cdot f(X)$, where I standardize such that $\mathbb{E}(f(X)) = 0$, and $\mathbb{V}(f(X)) = 1$. This is obviously a strong limitation on our class of possible functions, but it has two nice properties: First of all, the performance measures we will define depend only on s (given fixed residual distributions for ϵ_1, ϵ_0) and allow a comparison to established measures of effect size or signal strength from the literature. Secondly, the scale-families facilitate a glimpse on the mechanisms behind the second channel through which our second-best oracle loses power compared to the first-best interval. To be specific, we can target the following statistics,

$$(21) \quad \begin{aligned} s_{fb}(\beta) &\equiv \inf\{s \in \mathbb{R}_+ : F_{|\tau(X)|}^s(q_{1-\alpha}^{|\nu|}) \leq \beta\} \\ s_{sb}(\beta) &\equiv \inf\{s \in \mathbb{R}_+ : F_{|\tau(X)|}^s(q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_1|} + q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_0|}) \leq \beta\} \end{aligned}$$

where $\beta \in (0, 1)$ is a fixed type two error. Intuitively speaking, the two statistics measure how large we have to set the standard deviation of $\tau(\cdot)$ (which is s) in order to reach a certain power $1 - \beta$, for the two oracle procedures. The fraction between the two, i.e. $\frac{s_{sb}(\beta)}{s_{fb}(\beta)}$ is a convenient measure of how much larger a scale s (or a standard deviation) in the treatment our second-best oracle requires in order to reach the same power as the first-best oracle. Derivations on my part suggest that the fraction does not depend on β at all for our specific setup, and that it simplifies to the constant

$$\frac{s_{sb}(\beta)}{s_{fb}(\beta)} = \frac{q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_1|} + q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_0|}}{q_{1-\alpha}^{|\nu|}} = \mathcal{H}_\alpha. \quad 38$$

Note that since s is the standard deviation of τ , this measure can also be defined in a much more general context than the scale-family setup. However, the fact that $\frac{s_{sb}(\beta)}{s_{fb}(\beta)}$ coincides with \mathcal{H}_α does not have to generalize.

Given these insights, we can now look at how well our estimated prediction intervals C_Δ perform in simulations, and how much additional estimation error is introduced on top of C_{sb} .

4.4.2 Simulation setup and results

First of all and in reference to the traditional ATE framework, I use a class of ITEs with a constant (absolute) treatment effect whose magnitude we will increase in relation to the residual variances $\sigma_{\epsilon_1}, \sigma_{\epsilon_0}$. This setup can be achieved by a discrete scale-family to

³⁸This is proved in Theorem 6 in Appendix B.

generate τ , i.e.

$$\tau_1(X) = s \cdot f_1(X),$$

where $f_1(X) = \mathbb{1}(X(1) \geq 0) - \mathbb{1}(X(1) < 0)$, which implies $\mathbb{E}(f_1(X)) = 0$, $\mathbb{V}(f_1(X)) = 1$, given that $X(1)$ is the first component of a random vector $X \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I_{10})$.³⁹ Furthermore, we set $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_0 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ and vary the baseline main effect in (16) between

$$\begin{aligned} m_1(X) &= 1.0 \\ m_2(X) &= X^T \beta, \text{ where } \beta = (0, 1, 0, 1, \dots)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{10}, \\ m_3(X) &= 2 \cdot \log(1 + \exp(X^T \beta)) \end{aligned}$$

For a grid of $s \in \mathbb{R}_+$, we will evaluate the (empirical) power of our first-best oracle, and of the estimated conformal predictions intervals, among some additional metrics. Consequently, we can derive a measure similar to the *standardized* effect sizes $d(s)$, known as Cohen's d ,⁴⁰ in order to get an idea how large the (absolute) average effects would have to be to reach a prespecified power. To be specific, instead of the classical version of Cohen's d , defined as average treatment effect size (ATE) divided by pooled residual deviations, I will look at

$$\tilde{d} \equiv \frac{\mathbb{E}(|\tau(X)|)}{\sigma_{\epsilon_0}} = \frac{s}{\sigma_{\epsilon_0}}.$$

We can then empirically determine the minimal necessary \tilde{d} to achieve a target power $1 - \beta$, for our procedures. Naming that minimal value \tilde{d}_β , this enables a comparison with values for Cohen's d from the literature, keeping in mind that those are usually solely focused on the ATE as described before. Note that a calculation of \tilde{d}_β for the first-best oracle procedure yields $\tilde{d}_\beta^{fb} = s_{fb}(\beta)$, by definition (and since $\sigma_{\epsilon_0} = 1$), whereas for our estimated prediction intervals C_Δ , we expect $\tilde{d}_\beta^\Delta \geq s_{sb}(\beta) > s_{fb}(\beta)$, due to estimation error.

By increasing the sample size n and varying the complexity in the baseline main effect m , we can control the amount of estimation error of our estimated C_Δ and analyse its effect on \tilde{d}_β^Δ , compared to the inherent gap between $s_{fb}(\beta)$ and $s_{sb}(\beta)$. Similarly, I will compute \tilde{d}_β for the asymptotic procedure and the variants.

The second scenario takes the same specification in residuals ϵ_1, ϵ_0 and regressors X , but generates τ from a normal scale-family, i.e.

$$\tau_2(X) = s \cdot f_2(X),$$

³⁹If one wishes to closer replicate the traditional ATE framework for the sake of comparison, one could look at the non-random location model where we shift the ATE via a factor s , i.e. $Y(1) = m(X) + s + \epsilon_1$. This would yield exactly the same results as the discrete scale-model in our measures of interest, as additional simulations and intuition suggest.

⁴⁰This is due to Cohen (2013) and is a widely used metric in many fields of the empirical sciences.

where $f_2(X) = \frac{1}{5} \cdot X^T \tilde{\beta}$ and $\tilde{\beta} = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, \dots)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{10}$, such that again $\mathbb{E}(f_2(X)) = 0$, $\mathbb{V}(f_2(X)) = 1$. While the former discrete scenario puts all probability mass on $\{-s, s\}$, this normal scale-family setting induces smaller tail probabilities for τ , such that it is expected that for the same s we will have equal or less power across all procedures. Also, since the (absolute) treatment effect $|\tau_2(X)|$ is not constant anymore, \tilde{d} (and correspondingly \tilde{d}_β) is conceptually not the right tool in this setup, i.e. a comparison through Cohen's d is not appropriate. Consequently, we will motivate the comparisons by a signal-to-noise ratio instead, specified as

$$snr \equiv \frac{\sigma_\tau}{\sigma_{\epsilon_0}} = \frac{s}{\sigma_{\epsilon_0}}.$$

Since for the discrete scale-family, that is $\tau(X) = \tau_1(X)$, we have

$$snr \equiv \frac{\sigma_{\tau_1}}{\sigma_{\epsilon_0}} = \frac{s}{\sigma_{\epsilon_0}} = \frac{\mathbb{E}(|\tau_1(X)|)}{\sigma_{\epsilon_0}} \equiv \tilde{d}$$

we can restrict ourselves to snr in the outline of the simulation results. Analogous to before, for each oracle- or estimated prediction band procedure, let the minimal necessary snr to achieve a target power $1 - \beta$ be snr_β . Then, again due to $\epsilon_0 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, the snr_β 's for each oracle procedure translate directly into $s_{sb}(\beta)$, $s_{fb}(\beta)$ and \mathcal{H}_α , via (21).

Summary of setup specification. For the sake of clarity, let me summarize which setups we will consider, and which key objects of interest we will calculate:

- The combination of sample sizes $n \in \{2,000, 20,000\}$, baseline main effects $m \in \{m_1, m_2, m_3\}$, and CATEs $\tau \in \{\tau_1, \tau_2\}$, yields 12 simulation setups in total. Also, throughout we set $1 - \beta = 0.6$, $1 - \alpha = 0.9$, and generate $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_0 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, and $X \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I_{10})$. For each setup, we then vary s over a grid in $[1, 20]$ to determine our metrics of interest. Each simulation (for each setup and grid value s) is repeated 100 times, and the choice of an optimal base learner and the tuning of its hyperparameters is repeated in each first simulation run
- We calculate performance metrics for both the oracles, \mathcal{C}_{fb}^* and \mathcal{C}_{sb}^* , and our four estimated prediction bands, which are the simple procedure C_Δ , the asymptotic procedure \tilde{C}_Δ , the first variant C'_Δ , and the second variant \tilde{C}'_Δ . The score function for the W -conditional conformal intervals underlying the simple- and asymptotic procedure, is the mean-based score (\mathcal{C}_{split}^{mb}) from Chapter 3.4.1, while the counterfactual prediction intervals for the variants are naively constructed (see Appendix G)
- For each estimated prediction band procedure, \hat{C} , we target its average empirical coverage, $\gamma(\hat{C})$, its relative length with respect to the first-best oracle band, $\frac{l(\hat{C})}{l(\mathcal{C}_{fb}^*)}$, and its relative $snr_\beta^{\hat{C}}$ with respect to the first-best oracle's $snr_{0.6}^{fb} = s_{fb}(0.6)$, i.e. $\frac{snr_{0.6}^{\hat{C}}}{snr_{0.6}^{fb}}$. Additionally, I provide a mean squared error metric to quantify how well the

underlying conditional mean estimators have learned Δ_{n+1} , within each of the 12 setups.⁴¹

Results. Let us begin by comparing the oracle procedures with our simple- and asymptotic prediction bands. The second column in Table 1 portrays the length of the simple procedure relative to the first-best oracle. Recall from Section 4.4.1 that the lower bound on $l(C_\Delta)$ is given by the second-best oracle’s length, which in turn satisfies $\frac{l(C_{sb}^*)}{l(C_{fb}^*)} = \mathcal{H}_\alpha \approx 1.68$. This value only depends on the distributions ϵ_1, ϵ_0 , and is therefore constant across the 12 setups. As visible, $\frac{l(C_\Delta)}{l(C_{fb}^*)}$ approximates this lower bound as n increases or m turns less complex, no matter whether we are in the setting τ_1 or τ_2 . This is intuitive since again, $l(C_\Delta)$ only depends on our approximation of the (absolute) residual distributions. As our estimation error increases, the approximation gets worse and we widen the estimated prediction intervals. This reasoning is in line with an inspection of the relation between $\frac{l(C_\Delta)}{l(C_{fb}^*)}$ and the mean squared error metric in the first column: As we approach the lower bound of the $mse(\hat{\Delta})$,⁴² our $\frac{l(C_\Delta)}{l(C_{fb}^*)}$ converges to $\mathcal{H}_\alpha \approx 1.68$. Note that at least for the normal error distribution, a comparison of $\frac{l(C_\Delta)}{l(C_{fb}^*)}$ and $\frac{l(C_{sb}^*)}{l(C_{fb}^*)} \approx 1.68$ suggests that we only induce a small additional performance loss through estimation error for m_1 and m_2 , or large sample sizes n , while for the more complex setting m_3 the additional loss is comparable in size to the one generated by C_{sb}^* .

τ	n	m	$mse(\hat{\Delta})$	$\frac{l(C_\Delta)}{l(C_{fb}^*)}$	$\frac{l(\tilde{C}_\Delta)}{l(C_{fb}^*)}$	$snr_{0.6}^{fb}$	$\frac{snr_{0.6}^{sb}}{snr_{0.6}^{fb}}$	$\frac{snr_{0.6}^\Delta}{snr_{0.6}^{fb}}$	$\frac{snr_{0.6}^{\tilde{\Delta}}}{snr_{0.6}^{fb}}$	$\gamma(C_\Delta)$	$\gamma(\tilde{C}_\Delta)$
τ_1	2,000	m_1	2.03	1.71	1.01	2.32	1.68	1.78	1.06	0.99	0.90
		m_2	2.30	1.87	1.11	2.32	1.68	1.96	1.17	0.99	0.91
		m_3	2.77	2.24	1.31	2.32	1.68	2.38	1.42	1.0	0.93
	20,000	m_1	2.00	1.69	1.00	2.32	1.68	1.71	1.01	0.99	0.90
		m_2	2.07	1.72	1.02	2.32	1.68	1.79	1.06	0.99	0.90
		m_3	2.24	1.85	1.09	2.32	1.68	1.90	1.15	1.0	0.91
τ_2	2,000	m_1	2.03	1.71	1.01	4.43	1.68	1.71	1.01	0.99	0.90
		m_2	2.03	1.71	1.01	4.43	1.68	1.71	1.02	0.99	0.90
		m_3	2.41	2.45	1.41	4.43	1.68	2.49	1.43	1.0	0.97
	20,000	m_1	2.00	1.69	1.00	4.43	1.68	1.69	1.00	0.99	0.90
		m_2	2.00	1.69	1.01	4.43	1.68	1.69	1.01	0.99	0.90
		m_3	2.33	1.94	1.39	4.43	1.68	1.99	1.41	1.0	0.97

Table 1: Simulation results on performance metrics for the first-best oracle band, C_{fb}^* , the simple procedure, C_Δ , and the asymptotic procedure, \tilde{C}_Δ . Columns 1, 2, 3, 8, 9 are cross-section averages, taken over all s and repetitions, while the remaining columns represent empirical measures for a specific s (averaged over 100 repetitions).

⁴¹This is straightforward if we take the difference of the fitted conditional mean estimates $\hat{\mu}_1$ and $\hat{\mu}_0$ for the counterfactuals, and calculate the mean squared deviation to the actual realisations of Δ_{n+1} .

⁴²We have that $mse(\hat{\Delta}) \geq 2$ with high probability, since $\nu \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 2)$.

Next, consider the fourth column which contains first-best oracle results on minimal signal-to-noise ratios, snr_β , which is equivalent to \tilde{d} for the case $\tau(X) = \tau_1(X)$. These values are of interest themselves, since I wish to compare the optimal lower bound for any prediction interval for the ITE in our scale-family setting, to values from the literature. The results indicate that for the discrete scale-family, absolute effect sizes of more than two times the magnitude of residual standard deviations are necessary, to achieve substantial power with the first-best oracle procedure. Given that in the literature average effect sizes (Cohen’s d) starting from 0.8 upwards are considered large, one gets an idea about the residual variances’ impact on our inferential ability compared to traditional confidence regions. As discussed before, for the normal scale-family (τ_2) a comparison to Cohen’s d is misleading, but we can still state that a variance in our treatment effect signal of more than four times the residual variance’s size would be necessary, to achieve the desired power with our first-best oracle.

While there exist applications (especially in medicine and molecular biology) in which effect sizes of this magnitude can be of interest, the effect sizes necessary for detection with the second-best oracle, and consequently the simple procedure, are rather utopic. This becomes visible in the fifth and sixth column, where relative values larger or equal than 1.68 occur. This would render absolute values of $snr_{0.6}^\Delta$ into the range [3.96, 5.52] for the discrete-scale family (Cohen’s d applicable), and into the range [7.49, 11.03] for the normal-scale family. This is a major loss in power compared to the first-best oracle and can again largely be attributed to the specific way our simple prediction intervals are build, rather than it is a product of estimation error.⁴³ Fortunately, the asymptotic procedure seems to drastically shorten prediction intervals (third column) and consequently also performs well in terms of $\frac{snr_{0.6}^{\tilde{\Delta}}}{snr_{0.6}^{fb}}$ (seventh column), by effectively avoiding the induced conservativeness of the simple procedure and the second-best oracle. It even reaches the first-best oracle’s length (and $snr_{0.6}^{fb}$), in cases where the estimation error is low, and never surpasses the second-best oracles length (and $snr_{0.6}^{sb}$) when estimation error is large. Even the lack of a finite sample coverage guarantee is not visible in the results: the asymptotic procedure consistently maintains at least nominal coverage (ninth column), whereas the simple approach is super conservative (eighth column). One could argue that the sample sizes are too large and the estimation errors too small to make the asymptotic procedure undercover, however auxiliary simulations in Figure 10, Appendix C show that even for much smaller sample sizes, nominal coverage is maintained. An open question is whether our DGPs generally favour methods that rely on asymptotic results, or whether the suggested asymptotic procedure, \tilde{C}_Δ , has indeed good finite sample properties. This is where the variants, which should also exhibit an asymptotic coverage guarantee, come into play: As results in Table 2 demonstrate, the first variant suffers from the same conservative issues as the simple procedure, while the second variant fails to maintain

⁴³The gap between $snr_{0.6}^{fb}$ and $snr_{0.6}^{sb}$ is mostly larger than the gap between $snr_{0.6}^\Delta$ and $snr_{0.6}^{sb}$, with the only exception being the setup with complex baseline effect m_3 and small $n = 2,000$.

τ	n	m	$mse(\hat{\Delta})$	$\frac{l(\tilde{C}'_{\Delta})}{l(C'^*_{fb})}$	$\frac{l(C'_{\Delta})}{l(C'^*_{fb})}$	$\frac{snr_{0.6}^{\tilde{\Delta}'}}{snr_{0.6}^{fb}}$	$\frac{snr_{0.6}^{\Delta'_{\Delta}}}{snr_{0.6}^{fb}}$	$\gamma(\tilde{C}'_{\Delta})$	$\gamma(C'_{\Delta})$
τ_1	2,000	m_1	2.03	0.98	1.65	1.03	1.72	0.89	0.99
		m_2	2.30	0.92	1.55	0.98	1.63	0.84	0.98
		m_3	2.77	0.75	1.27	0.92	1.47	0.71	0.92
	20,000	m_1	2.00	0.99	1.68	1.01	1.69	0.89	0.99
		m_2	2.07	0.98	1.66	1.03	1.69	0.88	0.99
		m_3	2.24	0.92	1.55	0.97	1.59	0.85	0.98
τ_2	2,000	m_1	2.03	0.99	1.67	0.98	1.67	0.89	0.99
		m_2	2.03	0.99	1.67	0.99	1.69	0.89	0.99
		m_3	2.41	1.38	2.39	1.40	2.39	0.97	1.00
	20,000	m_1	2.00	0.99	1.68	1.00	1.69	0.89	0.99
		m_2	2.00	1.00	1.68	1.00	1.69	0.9	0.99
		m_3	2.33	1.39	2.42	1.39	2.39	0.97	1.00

Table 2: Simulation results on performance metrics for the two variants, \tilde{C}'_{Δ} , and C'_{Δ} . Columns 1, 2, 3, 6, 7 are cross-section averages, taken over all s and repetitions, while the remaining columns represent empirical measures for a specific s (averaged over 100 repetitions).

nominal coverage, exhibiting interval lengths that are in some setups even shorter than the first-best oracle. Another visible difference to the procedures from Table 1 is that both variants produce shorter interval lengths the larger the estimation error (first column) becomes. One potential explanation for this behavior is the automated choice of an optimal base learner algorithm (e.g. gradient boosting): The more difficult it is to estimate the regression surface, the more complex will the choice of the base learner be, and the more problematic is the risk of overfitting through hyperparameters. The overfitting can however introduce a downwards bias into our fitted residual distribution, when no conformalization is applied.

The results from Table 1 and Table 2 are supported by the full power curves⁴⁴ of our four candidate estimators (and a first-best oracle curve), which can be found in Figures 5 - 8 in Appendix C. While the asymptotic procedure often tends to the first-best oracle curve, the simple procedure's curve maintains a positive shift with respect to the oracle's curve even for simple DGPs and large samples. For the gaussian setups (right panels), the variants seem to be stable and to converge to the simple- and asymptotic procedure, respectively. However, in the discrete (τ_1) setups (left panels), the first variant's curve is usually in between the asymptotic's and the simple procedure's, while the second variant's curve is often shifted to the left of the oracle's, reflecting the fact of its undercoverage. Additionally, an instability of the variants' curves is apparent which is not due to outliers, but likely due to their sensitivity to hyperparameter tuning.⁴⁵

⁴⁴In this context this means the empirical counterpart of (15), in dependence of s .

⁴⁵The choice of a base learner, and tuning of its hyperparameters, happens every first run of the 100 repetitions for each s , and is held constant afterwards. Therefore, if the prediction band procedure

The last set of results can be found in Figures 9 - 10, where instead of varying the value of s , we vary n for insights on the behavior in small sample sizes. From the average coverage- and length graphs of each procedure, it is evident that

- The average interval lengths agree with the results from the Table 1 and Table 2, i.e. we usually observe $l(C_\Delta) > l(C'_\Delta) > l(\tilde{C}_\Delta) > l(\tilde{C}'_\Delta)$
- The average coverage of the simple procedure and the first variant is conservative, the asymptotic approach is generally maintaining nominal coverage and only becomes conservative for the complex setups, while the second variant usually undercovers, especially in small sample sizes

5 Conclusion

Conformal prediction intervals have recently experienced considerable attention by researchers, a development which is likely driven by their guaranteed finite sample coverage property, and the generality and simplicity of the method.

However, due to the marginal nature of the coverage guarantee of all conformal methods, J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018) recommend to use conformal prediction bands primarily as a diagnostic and comparison tool, since conformal methods can broaden the scope and value of any estimator (e.g. in regression, or quantile regression) at nearly no cost. The first part of my simulations, in which I compare some of the major competing conformal methods in the regression context, underlines this interpretation of J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018): In settings (M3) and (M4), where we either have high variance regions in the regression surface, or the target function is rather difficult to learn for our base-learners, we cannot expect any conformal method to work miracles in terms of conditional coverage across covariate space. Still, if we expect heteroscedasticity in our DGP, such that the optimal conditional length of prediction intervals across covariate space varies, simulation results and asymptotic theory suggest to prioritize the conformalized quantile regression by Romano, Patterson, and Candes (2019) over the ad hoc approach of locally-weighted mean-based intervals by J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018), as well as the seemingly conservative CDF based idea from Chernozhukov, Wüthrich, and Zhu (2019).

The second part of this thesis is focused on an interesting field of application of conformal inference, namely individual treatment effects within the potential outcome framework. Even though any coverage guarantee is again only marginal, we can hope that for a limited number of homogeneous strata, as is often the case in RCTs, we get close to an oracle which has conditional coverage. Consequently, we may ask how powerful prediction intervals for the ITE are, given that they include the residual variances. In the settings

is sensitive to changes in baseline hyperparameters, the lack of a conformalization step can introduce substantial undercoverage for all subsequent runs within this grid value s .

I consider, which are scale-families for the conditional average treatment effect, the absolute effect sizes (or the treatment-signal-to-noise ratios) which are necessary to reach meaningful power, are considerably larger than the ones common in the traditional literature. While there are fields with traditionally large effect sizes, where an oracle version of our prediction intervals for the ITE can be of use, the feasible simple procedure from Chapter 4.3 can be considered too conservative. However, a recently suggested alternative asymptotic procedure which guarantees coverage only in the limit and under stronger assumptions, performs surprisingly well in small samples, by drastically reducing interval lengths and nearly always maintaining nominal coverage.

Therefore, I conclude that conformal inference within the potential outcome framework, and in general, remains a promising area of research. In the treatment effect context, further generalizations of the concept to observational studies, in the spirit of L. Lei and Candès (2020), are of considerable interest. While the inherent variation in the ITE makes predictive inference in small effect size regimes difficult, the conformal approach can also be viewed as an additional safety check to exclude negative effects on an individual level which stem from the remaining residual variance and are therefore neglected by traditional confidence intervals based on the CATE. This is particularly relevant in high-risk settings in medicine.

A Notation

Symbols

$R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i)$	the rank of U_i with respect to the set $\{U_1, \dots, U_{n+1}\}$
$\{X_j, Y_j\}_{-i}$	the set $\{(X_1, Y_1), \dots, (X_{i-1}, Y_{i-1}), (X_{i+1}, Y_{i+1}), \dots, (X_n, Y_n)\}$
Δ_{n+1}	the individual treatment effect for a new observation
β_{ITE}	probability of a false negative for the ITE prediction interval
β_{ATE}	probability of a false negative for the ATE confidence interval

Abbreviations

DGP	data generating process
ATE	average treatment effect
ITE	individual treatment effect
CATE	conditional average treatment effect
<i>snr</i>	signal-to-noise ratio

B Proofs

Proof of Lemma 1. Since U_1, U_2, \dots, U_{n+1} is a finitely exchangeable sequence it follows that the rank statistics $R_{1:(n+1)}(U_1), \dots, R_{1:(n+1)}(U_{n+1})$ are identically distributed. Fix $k \in \{1, \dots, n+1\}$. Due to being identically distributed and being a discrete random variable over $\{1, \dots, n+1\}$, we have

$$\mathbb{P}(R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i) = k) = \mathbb{P}(R_{1:(n+1)}(U_j) = k), \quad \forall i, j \in \{1, \dots, n+1\}$$

By assumption $\mathbb{P}\{U_i = U_j\} = 0$, $i \neq j$. Therefore, the rank statistics are almost surely distinct, and the events of the form

$$\{R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i) = k\}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n+1$$

form a partition of the outcome space. Therefore, $\sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \mathbb{P}(\{R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i) = k\}) = 1$ and thus

$$\mathbb{P}(R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i) = k) = \frac{1}{n+1}.$$

Since the choice of k was arbitrary, $R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i)$ is uniformly distributed on $\{1, \dots, n+1\}$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n+1\}$.

For the second part I distinguish two cases: Suppose first we are in the case where $n+1 < t$.

Since $R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i)$ takes on only values in $\{1, \dots, n+1\}$, it is obvious that

$$\mathbb{P}\left(R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i) \leq t\right) = \mathbb{P}\left(R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i) \leq n+1\right) = 1 = \min\left\{\frac{\lfloor t \rfloor}{n+1}, 1\right\}$$

In the more interesting case where $t \leq n+1$, we have by the first part above that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}\left(R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i) \leq t\right) &= \mathbb{P}\left(R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i) \leq \lfloor t \rfloor\right) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{\lfloor t \rfloor} \mathbb{P}\left(R_{1:(n+1)}(U_i) = j\right) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{\lfloor t \rfloor} \frac{1}{n+1} = \frac{\lfloor t \rfloor}{n+1} = \min\left\{\frac{\lfloor t \rfloor}{n+1}, 1\right\}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Proof of Theorem 1. Note that the event of interest can be rewritten as follows

$$\begin{aligned} &Y_{n+1} \in \mathcal{C}_{full}(X_{n+1}) \\ \iff &Y_{n+1} \in \left\{y \in \mathbb{R} : R_{1:(n+1)}\left(V_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, y)}\right) \leq \lceil (1-\alpha)(n+1) \rceil\right\} \\ \iff &R_{1:(n+1)}\left(V_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1})}\right) \leq \lceil (1-\alpha)(n+1) \rceil \end{aligned}$$

Now observe that since $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^{n+1}$ are assumed exchangeable, it follows that $V_1^{(X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1})}, \dots, V_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1})}$ are also exchangeable, by the symmetric construction of the nonconformity scores. Since by assumption no ties occur in this sequence of nonconformity scores, a direct application of Lemma 1, with $t = \lceil (n+1)(1-\alpha) \rceil$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, yields after simplification

$$\mathbb{P}\left(R_{1:(n+1)}\left(V_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1})}\right) \leq \lceil (n+1)(1-\alpha) \rceil\right) = \frac{\lceil (n+1)(1-\alpha) \rceil}{n+1}$$

and thus

$$1 - \alpha \leq \frac{\lceil (n+1)(1-\alpha) \rceil}{n+1} \leq 1 - \alpha + \frac{1}{n+1}.$$

which concludes the proof. □

Proof of Theorem 2. We can write out the event of interest as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} &Y_{n+1} \in \left\{y \in \mathbb{R} : \tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, y)} \leq V_{(k)}\right\} \\ \iff &\tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1})} \leq V_{(k)} \end{aligned}$$

where $k = \lceil (1-\alpha)(|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1) \rceil$, and $V_{(k)}$ is the k -th order statistic of the set $\{\tilde{V}_i : i \in \mathcal{I}_2\}$.

The crucial step at this point is to observe that the following holds,

$$\tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1})} \leq V_{(k)} \iff R_{\mathcal{I}_2 \cup (n+1)} \left(\tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1})} \right) \leq k$$

which can easily be proven or looked up, e.g. Lemma 2 (on inflated empirical quantiles) in Romano, Patterson, and Candes (2019). Note that the rank $R_{\mathcal{I}_2 \cup (n+1)} \left(\tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1})} \right)$ is computed over the set of variables $\{\tilde{V}_i : i \in \mathcal{I}_2\} \cup \{\tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1})}\}$, while the order statistic is based on reduced set $\{\tilde{V}_i : i \in \mathcal{I}_2\}$.

Since $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^{n+1}$ are assumed exchangeable, it follows that $\{\tilde{V}_i : i \in \mathcal{I}_2\} \cup \{\tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1})}\}$ are also exchangeable, by the symmetric construction of the nonconformity scores. Since by assumption no ties occur in this sequence of nonconformity scores, a direct application of Lemma 1, with $t = k = \lceil (|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1)(1 - \alpha) \rceil$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, yields after simplification

$$\mathbb{P} \left(R_{\mathcal{I}_2 \cup (n+1)} \left(\tilde{V}_{n+1}^{(X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1})} \right) \leq \lceil (|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1)(1 - \alpha) \rceil \right) = \frac{\lceil (|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1)(1 - \alpha) \rceil}{|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1}$$

and thus

$$1 - \alpha \leq \frac{\lceil (|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1)(1 - \alpha) \rceil}{|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1} \leq 1 - \alpha + \frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1}.$$

which concludes the proof. \square

Theorem 6. *In our semiparametric specification of the potential outcomes from Chapter 4.4.1, fix the residual distributions of ϵ_1, ϵ_0 , and let τ be generated from some scale-family, i.e.*

$$\tau(X) = s \cdot f(X),$$

where $s > 0$ and we standardize $f(X)$ such that $\mathbb{E}(f(X)) = 0$ and $\mathbb{V}(f(X)) = 1$. Reconsider the following measures,

$$\begin{aligned} s_{fb}(\beta) &\equiv \inf\{s \in \mathbb{R}_+ : F_{|\tau(X)|}^s(q_{1-\alpha}^{|\nu|}) \leq \beta\} \\ s_{sb}(\beta) &\equiv \inf\{s \in \mathbb{R}_+ : F_{|\tau(X)|}^s(q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_1|} + q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_0|}) \leq \beta\} \end{aligned}$$

where $\beta \in (0, 1)$ is a fixed type two error. Then it follows that the fraction $\frac{s_{sb}(\beta)}{s_{fb}(\beta)}$ is well-defined, independent of the value β , and takes the form

$$\frac{s_{sb}(\beta)}{s_{fb}(\beta)} = \frac{q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_1|} + q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_0|}}{q_{1-\alpha}^{|\nu|}} = \mathcal{H}_\alpha.$$

Proof of Theorem 6. First of all, note that due to τ being part of the scale-family induced by $f(X)$, we have by definition that its cumulative distribution function obeys $F_{\tau(X)}(y) = F_{f(X)}\left(\frac{y}{s}\right)$. Furthermore, since $s > 0$, we have

$$|\tau(X)| = s \cdot |f(X)|$$

such that also $F_{|\tau(X)|}(y) = F_{|f(X)|}\left(\frac{y}{s}\right)$. This implies that we can rewrite the above measures as

$$s_{fb}(\beta) \equiv \inf \left\{ s \in \mathbb{R}_+ : F_{|f(X)|}^s \left(\frac{\bar{b}}{s} \right) \leq \beta \right\}$$

$$s_{sb}(\beta) \equiv \inf \left\{ s \in \mathbb{R}_+ : F_{|f(X)|}^s \left(\frac{\bar{a}}{s} \right) \leq \beta \right\}$$

where I simplified notation such that $\bar{b} = q_{1-\alpha}^{|\nu|}$ and $\bar{a} = q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_1|} + q_{1-\alpha/2}^{|\epsilon_0|}$. These two infima exist, since the sets are by construction bounded below by zero, and non-empty, since $F_{|f(X)|}^s \left(\frac{k}{s} \right) \xrightarrow{s \rightarrow \infty} 0$, for any $k \in \mathbb{R}_+$. For the fraction (and the following statements) to be well-defined, we need that $s_{fb}(\beta), s_{sb}(\beta) > 0$. But this follows immediately, since $\beta < 1$, and we observe that $F_{|f(X)|}^s \left(\frac{k}{s} \right) \xrightarrow{s \rightarrow 0} 1$, for any $k \in \mathbb{R}_+$. This implies that for every k , there must be some small $s_k > 0$ for which $F_{|f(X)|} \left(\frac{k}{s_k} \right) > \beta$.

For the final part, we can thus assume the existence of some $s_{fb}(\beta) > 0$, abbreviated as s_{fb} in the following. The infimum preserves the weak inequality, such that $F_{|f(X)|} \left(\frac{\bar{b}}{s_{fb}} \right) \leq \beta$. Now observe that since $\frac{\bar{b}}{s_{fb}} \in \mathbb{R}_+$, we can find some $s' \in \mathbb{R}_+$, such that

$$\frac{\bar{a}}{s'} = \frac{\bar{b}}{s_{fb}}.$$

We claim that $s_{sb}(\beta) = s'$, i.e. s' is claimed to satisfy

$$s' = \inf \left\{ s \in \mathbb{R}_+ : F_{|f(X)|}^s \left(\frac{\bar{a}}{s} \right) \leq \beta \right\}.$$

Suppose not, then there exists some $s'' < s'$ such that $F_{|f(X)|} \left(\frac{\bar{a}}{s''} \right) \leq \beta$. From this, we get the relation

$$\frac{\bar{a}}{s''} > \frac{\bar{a}}{s'} = \frac{\bar{b}}{s_{fb}}.$$

But in this case there exists some $s''' < s_{fb}$, such that

$$\frac{\bar{b}}{s'''} = \frac{\bar{a}}{s''}$$

and thus

$$F_{|f(X)|} \left(\frac{\bar{b}}{s'''} \right) = F_{|f(X)|} \left(\frac{\bar{a}}{s''} \right) \leq \beta.$$

This is a contradiction since we assumed that s_{fb} is the infimum of the set $\left\{ s \in \mathbb{R}_+ : F_{|f(X)|}^s \left(\frac{\bar{b}}{s} \right) \leq \beta \right\}$, but now have found a smaller element that is part of the set. Therefore, our claim follows, which is

$$\frac{\bar{a}}{s_{sb}} = \frac{\bar{b}}{s_{fb}}.$$

This equality does not depend on β and yields the desired statement after rearrangement.

C Additional tables and figures

	n	method	mean length	mean coverage
DGP 1	1,000	M1	1.99	0.901
		M2	1.68	0.901
		M3	1.69	0.896
		M4	1.79	0.906
		M5	1.64	0.900
DGP 2	1,000	M1	2.67	0.901
		M2	2.99	0.900
		M3	2.57	0.901
		M4	3.9	0.902
		M5	2.24	0.900
DGP 3	1,000	M1	13.97	0.905
		M2	13.13	0.901
		M3	13.09	0.899
		M4	14.06	0.899
		M5	12.71	0.900
DGP 4	5,000	M1	10.25	0.897
		M2	10.24	0.902
		M3	10.44	0.902
		M4	10.62	0.902
		M5	8.92	0.900

Table 3: Simulations results from Section 3.5 on average length- and coverage of various prediction intervals across different DGPs. Averaged over 250 repetitions and 300 predicted intervals each.

Figure 1: Simulation results from Section 3.5 for DGP1, averaged over 250 repetitions and 300 predicted intervals each. *Left*: Kernel estimates of the length of prediction intervals conditional on the regressor X , for each of the procedures. *Right*: Kernel estimates of the coverage of prediction intervals conditional on the regressor X , scale on the left y-axis. An additional plot of the conditional variance with the scale on the right y-axis.

Figure 2: Simulation results from Section 3.5 for DGP2, averaged over 250 repetitions and 300 predicted intervals each. *Left*: Kernel estimates of the length of prediction intervals conditional on the regressor X , for each of the procedures. *Right*: Kernel estimates of the coverage of prediction intervals conditional on the regressor X , scale on the left y-axis. An additional plot of the conditional variance with the scale on the right y-axis.

Figure 3: Simulation results from Section 3.5 for DGP3, averaged over 250 repetitions and 300 predicted intervals each. *Left*: Kernel estimates of the length of prediction intervals conditional on $\beta^T X$, for each of the procedures. *Right*: Kernel estimates of the coverage of prediction intervals conditional on $\beta^T X$, scale on the left y-axis. An additional plot of the conditional variance with the scale on the right y-axis. Additional scatter on the x-axis as an approximate display of the distribution of $\beta^T X$.

Figure 4: Simulation results from Section 3.5 for DGP4, averaged over 250 repetitions and 300 predicted intervals each. *Left*: Kernel estimates of the length of prediction intervals conditional on $\beta^T X$, for each of the procedures. *Right*: Kernel estimates of the coverage of prediction intervals conditional on $\beta^T X$, scale on the left y-axis. An additional plot of the conditional variance with the scale on the right y-axis. Additional scatter on the x-axis as an approximate display of the distribution of $\beta^T X$.

Figure 5: Power simulation curves for $n = 2,000$ and the prediction bands \mathcal{C}_{fb}^* , C_Δ , and \tilde{C}_Δ . Each of the 6 panels visualizes results for a combination of a baseline effects, m , and conditional treatment effect function, τ . The x -axis represents the grid on which s , the scale factor of the treatment effect, is varied. The y -axis gives values for the (empirical) power for each method. *Blue graph*: Power of the first-best oracle (\mathcal{C}_{fb}^*) as defined in (17). *Orange graph*: Power of the simple procedure (C_Δ). *Green graph*: Power of the asymptotic procedure (\tilde{C}_Δ).

Figure 6: Power simulation curves for $n = 20,000$ and the prediction bands \mathcal{C}_{fb}^* , C_Δ , and \tilde{C}_Δ . Each of the 6 panels visualizes results for a combination of a baseline effects, m , and conditional treatment effect function, τ . The x -axis represents the grid on which s , the scale factor of the treatment effect, is varied. The y -axis gives values for the (empirical) power for each method. *Blue graph*: Power of the first-best oracle (\mathcal{C}_{fb}^*) as defined in (17). *Orange graph*: Power of the simple procedure (C_Δ). *Green graph*: Power of the asymptotic procedure (\tilde{C}_Δ).

Figure 7: Extended power simulation curves for $n = 2,000$ and the prediction bands C_{fb}^* , C_Δ , \tilde{C}_Δ , C'_Δ , and \tilde{C}'_Δ . Each of the 6 panels visualizes results for a combination of a baseline effects, m , and conditional treatment effect function, τ . The x -axis represents the grid on which s , the scale factor of the treatment effect, is varied. The y -axis gives values for the (empirical) power for each method. *Blue graph*: First-best oracle (C_{fb}^*). *Orange graph*: Simple procedure (C_Δ). *Green graph*: Asymptotic procedure (\tilde{C}_Δ). *Red graph*: First variant (C'_Δ). *Purple graph*: Second variant (\tilde{C}'_Δ).

Figure 8: Extended power simulation curves for $n = 20,000$ and the prediction bands C_{fb}^* , C_Δ , \tilde{C}_Δ , C'_Δ , and \tilde{C}'_Δ . Each of the 6 panels visualizes results for a combination of a baseline effects, m , and conditional treatment effect function, τ . The x -axis represents the grid on which s , the scale factor of the treatment effect, is varied. The y -axis gives values for the (empirical) power for each method. *Blue graph*: First-best oracle (C_{fb}^*). *Orange graph*: Simple procedure (C_Δ). *Green graph*: Asymptotic procedure (\tilde{C}_Δ). *Red graph*: First variant (C'_Δ). *Purple graph*: Second variant (\tilde{C}'_Δ).

Figure 9: Average length of ITE intervals, for varying sample size. *Orange graph*: Simple procedure (C_Δ). *Green graph*: Asymptotic procedure (\tilde{C}_Δ). *Red graph*: First variant (C'_Δ). *Purple graph*: Second variant (\tilde{C}'_Δ). For the left panels (discrete treatment effect), s was fixed to $s = 2.32$; for the right panels (gaussian treatment effect), s was fixed to $s = 4.43$.

Figure 10: Average coverage of ITE intervals, for varying sample size. *Orange graph:* Simple procedure (C_{Δ}). *Green graph:* Asymptotic procedure (\tilde{C}_{Δ}). *Red graph:* First variant (C'_{Δ}). *Purple graph:* Second variant (\tilde{C}'_{Δ}). For the left panels (discrete treatment effect), s was fixed to $s = 2.32$; for the right panels (gaussian treatment effect), s was fixed to $s = 4.43$.

distribution	σ_ϵ	\mathcal{H}_α
<i>normal</i>	0.5	1.68
	1.0	1.68
	2.0	1.68
<i>t-distr.</i>	-	-
	-	-
	2.0	1.84
<i>uniform</i>	0.5	1.39
	1.0	1.39
	2.0	1.39
<i>hyperbolic</i> <i>secant</i>	0.5	1.79
	1.0	1.79
	2.0	1.79

Table 4: Simulations results from Section 4.4.2 on the measure \mathcal{H}_α for various types of symmetric error distributions and different residual variances. Recall that \mathcal{H}_α is a measure of the first-channel through which the second-best oracle band on the ITE can experience a loss in power in comparison to the first-best oracle band. Values are between (1, 2) and do often not vary within a given residual distribution, when changing the variance σ_ϵ^2 . The only exception among those four in that respect is the *t*-distribution, which for larger variances (not shown in table) exhibits increasing \mathcal{H}_α .

Figure 11: Additional simulations results for Section 4.4.1, depicting the dependence of \mathcal{H}_α on α , given $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_0 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. At least for the normal case, the higher we set our α , the larger is our \mathcal{H}_α .

D Data generating processes

D.1 Heteroskedasticity simulations

DGP1: (as in Chernozhukov, Wüthrich, and Zhu (2019))

$$Y_i = X_i + X_i \epsilon,$$

$$\text{s.t. } X_i \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1) \wedge \epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$$

DGP2: (as in Romano, Patterson, and Candes (2019))

$$Y_i = \text{Pois}(\sin^2(X_i) + 0.1) + 0.03 \cdot X_i \epsilon_{1,i} + 25 \cdot \mathbb{1}_{U_i \leq 0.01} \epsilon_{2,i}$$

$$\text{s.t. } X_i \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 5) \wedge U_i \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1) \wedge \epsilon_{1,i}, \epsilon_{2,i} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$$

DGP3: (as in J. Lei, G'Sell, et al. (2018))

$$Y_i = \beta' X_i + \epsilon \left(1 + \frac{2 \cdot |\beta' X_i|^3}{\mathbb{E}[|\beta' X_i|^3]} \right),$$

$$\text{s.t. } Y_i, X_i \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^{10},$$

$$U_i(k) \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1), \quad 1 \leq k \leq 10,$$

$$\tilde{X}_i(k) \sim \mathbb{1}_{U_i \leq \frac{1}{3}} \mathcal{N}(0, 1) + \mathbb{1}_{\frac{1}{3} \leq U_i \leq \frac{2}{3}} \mathcal{SN}(0, 1, 5) + \mathbb{1}_{U_i \geq \frac{2}{3}} \mathcal{B}(0.5),$$

$$X_i = \tilde{X}_i \Sigma^{0.5}, \quad \Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \rho & \cdots & \rho \\ \rho & 1 & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \rho \\ \rho & \cdots & \rho & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{10 \times 10}, \quad \rho = 0.15,$$

$$\epsilon \sim t(4), \quad \beta = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, \dots, 0) \in \mathbb{R}^{10}$$

DGP4: (as in Kivaranovic, Johnson, and Leeb (2020))

$$Y_i = 2 \cdot \sin(\pi \cdot \beta' X_i) + \pi \cdot \beta' X_i + \epsilon \sqrt{1 + (\beta' X_i)^2},$$

$$\text{s.t. } Y_i, X_i \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^{100} \wedge X_i \sim \mathcal{U}([0, 1]^{100}),$$

$$\beta = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, \dots, 0) \in \mathbb{R}^{100} \wedge \epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$$

E Algorithms

Algorithm 1: Mean-based full conformal method

Data: $(X_i, Y_i), i = 1, \dots, n$, miscoverage level $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, regression algorithm \mathcal{A} ,
new points $X_{new} = \{X_{n+1}, X_{n+2}, \dots\}$, and values $Y_{trial} = \{y_1, y_2, \dots\}$

Result: Predictions intervals, at each element of X_{new}

for $x \in X_{new}$ **do**

for $y \in Y_{trial}$ **do**

- $\hat{\mu}_y = \mathcal{A}(\{(X_1, Y_1), \dots, (X_n, Y_n), (x, y)\})$
- $V_i^{(x,y)} = |Y_i - \hat{\mu}_y(X_i)|, i = 1, \dots, n \wedge V_{n+1}^{(x,y)} = |y - \hat{\mu}_y(x)|$
- $R_{1:(n+1)}(V_{n+1}^{(x,y)}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \mathbb{1} \left\{ V_i^{(x,y)} \leq V_{n+1}^{(x,y)} \right\}$

end

$$\mathcal{C}_{full}^{mb}(x) = \left\{ y \in Y_{trial} : R_{1:(n+1)}(V_{n+1}^{(x,y)}) \leq \lceil (1 - \alpha)(n + 1) \rceil \right\}$$

end

Return $\mathcal{C}_{full}^{mb}(x)$ for each $x \in X_{new}$

Algorithm 2: Mean-based split conformal method

Data: $(X_i, Y_i), i = 1, \dots, n$, miscoverage level $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, regression algorithm \mathcal{A}

Result: Predictions band over $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$

- Randomly split $\{1, \dots, n\}$ into two subsets $\mathcal{I}_1, \mathcal{I}_2$
- $\hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1} = \mathcal{A}(\{(X_i, Y_i) : i \in \mathcal{I}_1\})$
- $\tilde{V}_i = |Y_i - \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_i)|, i \in \mathcal{I}_2$
- $V_{(k)}$ = the k -th smallest value (k -th order statistic) in $\{\tilde{V}_i : i \in \mathcal{I}_2\}$, where $k = \lceil (1 - \alpha)(|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1) \rceil$

Return $\mathcal{C}_{split}^{mb}(x) = [\hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(x) - V_{(k)}, \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(x) + V_{(k)}]$

Algorithm 3: Locally-weighted split conformal method

Data: $(X_i, Y_i), i = 1, \dots, n$, miscoverage level $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, regression algorithms $\mathcal{A}_1,$
 \mathcal{A}_2

Result: Predictions band over $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$

- Randomly split $\{1, \dots, n\}$ into two subsets $\mathcal{I}_1, \mathcal{I}_2$
- $\hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1} = \mathcal{A}_1(\{(X_i, Y_i) : i \in \mathcal{I}_1\})$
- $\hat{\rho}_{\mathcal{I}_1} = \mathcal{A}_2(\{(X_i, Y_i) : i \in \mathcal{I}_1\})$, where $\rho(x) = \mathbb{E}[|Y - \mu(X)| \mid X = x]$
- $\tilde{V}_i = \frac{|Y_i - \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_i)|}{\hat{\rho}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(X_i)}, i \in \mathcal{I}_2$
- $V_{(k)}$ = the k -th smallest value in $\{\tilde{V}_i : i \in \mathcal{I}_2\}$, where $k = \lceil (1 - \alpha)(|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1) \rceil$

Return

$$\mathcal{C}_{split}^{wmb}(x) = [\hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(x) - \hat{\rho}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(x)V_{(k)}, \hat{\mu}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(x) + \hat{\rho}_{\mathcal{I}_1}(x)V_{(k)}], x \in \mathbb{R}^d$$

Algorithm 4: Quantile regression (split) conformal method

Data: $(X_i, Y_i), i = 1, \dots, n$, miscoverage level $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, quantile regression algorithms $\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{A}_2$

Result: Predictions band over $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$

- Randomly split $\{1, \dots, n\}$ into two subsets $\mathcal{I}_1, \mathcal{I}_2$
- $\hat{q}_{\alpha/2} = \mathcal{A}_1(\{(X_i, Y_i) : i \in \mathcal{I}_1\})$
- $\hat{q}_{1-\alpha/2} = \mathcal{A}_2(\{(X_i, Y_i) : i \in \mathcal{I}_1\})$
- $\tilde{V}_i = \max\{\hat{q}_{\alpha/2}(X_i) - Y_i, Y_i - \hat{q}_{1-\alpha/2}(X_i)\}, i \in \mathcal{I}_2$
- $V_{(k)}$ = the k -th smallest value in $\{\tilde{V}_i : i \in \mathcal{I}_2\}$, where $k = \lceil(1 - \alpha)(|\mathcal{I}_2| + 1)\rceil$.

Return

$$\hat{\mathcal{C}}_{split}^{qb}(X_{n+1}) = [\hat{q}_{\alpha/2}(X_{n+1}) - V_{(k)}, \hat{q}_{1-\alpha/2}(X_{n+1}) + V_{(k)}]$$

Algorithm 5: CDF based (split) conformal method

Data: $(X_i, Y_i), i = 1, \dots, n$, miscoverage level $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, regression algorithm \mathcal{A} for the conditional CDF, $F_{Y|X}$, new points $X_{new} = \{X_{n+1}, X_{n+2}, \dots\}$, and values $Y_{trial} = \{y_1, y_2, \dots\}$

Result: Predictions intervals, at each element of X_{new}

- Randomly split $\{1, \dots, n\}$ into two subsets $\mathcal{I}_1, \mathcal{I}_2$
- $\hat{F}_{Y|X} = \mathcal{A}(\{(X_i, Y_i) : i \in \mathcal{I}_1\})$

for $x \in X_{new}$ **do**

for $y \in Y_{trial}$ **do**

- Define $\mathcal{I}_{2,(x,y)} \equiv \mathcal{I}_2 \cup \{(x, y)\}$
- Compute $\hat{V}_{y,i} = |\hat{F}_{Y|X}(Y_i, X_i) - 0.5|, i \in \mathcal{I}_2$
and $\hat{V}_{y,n+1} = |\hat{F}_{Y|X}(y, x) - 0.5|$
- $R_{\mathcal{I}_{2,(x,y)}}(\hat{V}_{y,n+1}) = \sum_{\mathcal{I}_{2,(x,y)}} \mathbb{1}(\hat{V}_{y,i} \leq \hat{V}_{y,n+1})$

end

$$\mathcal{C}_{split}^{cdf}(x) = \left\{ y \in Y_{trial} : R_{\mathcal{I}_{2,(x,y)}}(\hat{V}_{y,n+1}) \leq \lceil(1 - \alpha)(n + 1)\rceil \right\}$$

end

Return $\mathcal{C}_{split}^{cdf}(x)$ for each $x \in X_{new}$

F Electronic Appendix

Code for the conformal methods and the replication of basic simulation results can be found under <https://github.com/JosefNagelschmidt/conformal-inference>.

G Additional Material

G.1 Exchangeability

Definition 3. *Random variables U_1, \dots, U_n are said to be exchangeable if*

$$(U_1, \dots, U_n) \stackrel{d}{=} (U_{\pi(1)}, \dots, U_{\pi(n)})$$

where $\pi : \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, n\}$ is an arbitrary permutation of indices.

G.2 Variants for the ITE prediction intervals

G.2.1 First variant

Recall that in the *simple procedure* from Chapter 4.3 we used the level- $(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2})$ W -conditional conformal prediction intervals for the counterfactuals, i.e.

$$C_w(X_{n+1}) = [l_w(X_{n+1}), u_w(X_{n+1})] \quad (w = 0, 1)$$

and generated the prediction interval on Δ_{n+1} by setting

$$C_\Delta(X_{n+1}) \equiv [l_1(X_{n+1}) - u_0(X_{n+1}), u_1(X_{n+1}) - l_0(X_{n+1})]$$

In the *first variant*, we replace these W -conditional conformal prediction intervals by

$$\mathcal{C}_w^{\text{naive}}(X_{n+1}) = \left[\hat{\mu}_w(X_{n+1}) - \hat{q}_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\hat{\epsilon}_w|}, \hat{\mu}_w(X_{n+1}) + \hat{q}_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\hat{\epsilon}_w|} \right] \quad (w = 0, 1)$$

where $\hat{q}_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\hat{\epsilon}_w|}$ is the $(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2})$ -quantile of the empirical distribution of fitted absolute residuals (in the treatment, or control group), and $\hat{\mu}_w$ an estimator of the conditional expectation function (in the treatment or control group). This naive usage of residuals that are calculated on the same sample which was used for fitting $\hat{\mu}_w$, will typically lead to under-coverage in finite samples. However, the approach can become valid for large samples, if the estimated regression function $\hat{\mu}_w$ is consistent, such that $\hat{q}_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^{|\hat{\epsilon}_w|}$ approximates the corresponding population quantile. Note that under consistency, these naive counterfactual prediction intervals converge to their homoscedastic oracle counterparts, as defined in (6).

G.2.2 Second variant

The second variant functions similarly, but instead of replacing the level- $(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2})$ W -conditional conformal prediction intervals in the simple method, we replace the level- $(1 - \alpha)$ W -conditional conformal prediction intervals from the *asymptotic procedure* with

$$\mathcal{C}_w^{\text{naive}}(X_{n+1}) = \left[\hat{\mu}_w(X_{n+1}) - \hat{q}_{1-\alpha}^{|\hat{\epsilon}_w|}, \hat{\mu}_w(X_{n+1}) + \hat{q}_{1-\alpha}^{|\hat{\epsilon}_w|} \right] \quad (w = 0, 1)$$

G.3 Marginal coverage of the homoscedastic oracle

Given $(X, Y) \sim \mathcal{P}_{XY}$, whenever we can apply the law of iterated expectations, the conditional expectation function decomposition property holds, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} Y &= \mathbb{E}[Y | X] + \epsilon \\ &= \mu(X) + \epsilon, \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbb{E}[\epsilon | X] = 0$. Further, since $(X_i, Y_i)_{i=1}^{n+1} \stackrel{i.i.d.}{\sim} \mathcal{P}_{XY}$, this decomposition holds also for the new draw (X_{n+1}, Y_{n+1}) , such that we can reformulate the event of interest into

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{n+1} &\in \mathcal{C}^*(X_{n+1}) \\ \iff Y_{n+1} &\in \left[\mu(X_{n+1}) - q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|}, \mu(X_{n+1}) + q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|} \right] \\ \iff \mu(X_{n+1}) - q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|} &\leq Y_{n+1} \leq \mu(X_{n+1}) + q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|} \\ \iff -q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|} &\leq Y_{n+1} - \mu(X_{n+1}) \leq q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|} \\ \iff -q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|} &\leq \epsilon_{n+1} \leq q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|} \\ \iff |\epsilon_{n+1}| &\leq q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|}. \end{aligned}$$

By the properties of the generalized inverse distribution function, \tilde{F}^{-1} , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}\left(|\epsilon_{n+1}| \leq q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|}\right) &= F_{|\epsilon|}\left(q_{1-\alpha}^{|\epsilon|}\right) \\ &= F_{|\epsilon|}\left(\tilde{F}_{|\epsilon|}^{-1}[1 - \alpha]\right) \\ &\geq 1 - \alpha. \end{aligned}$$

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Statutory Declaration

Ich versichere hiermit, dass ich die vorstehende Masterarbeit selbstständig verfasst und keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt habe, dass die vorgelegte Arbeit noch an keiner anderen Hochschule zur Prüfung vorgelegt wurde und dass sie weder ganz noch in Teilen bereits veröffentlicht wurde. Wörtliche Zitate und Stellen, die anderen Werken dem Sinn nach entnommen sind, habe ich in jedem einzelnen Fall kenntlich gemacht.

Bonn, 29.09.2021